

INTEGRATING PROVENANCE CAPTURE AND UML WITH UML2PROV: PRINCIPLES AND EXPERIENCE

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Carlos Sáenz-Adán^{1*}, Beatriz Pérez¹, Francisco J. García-Izquierdo¹, Luc Moreau²

¹Dept. of Mathematics and Computer Science, Univ. of La Rioja, La Rioja, Spain,
{carlos.saenz,beatriz.perez,francisco.garcia}@unirioja.es

²Dept. of Informatics, King's College London, London, UK,
luc.moreau@kcl.ac.uk

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INTEGRATING PROVENANCE CAPTURE AND UML WITH UML2PROV: PRINCIPLES AND EXPERIENCE

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SPECIFICATION OF THE UML TO PROV PATTERNS

Carlos Sáenz-Adán^{1*}, Beatriz Pérez¹, Francisco J. García-Izquierdo¹, Luc Moreau²

¹Dept. of Mathematics and Computer Science, Univ. of La Rioja, La Rioja, Spain,
{carlos.saenz,beatriz.perez,francisco.garcia}@unirioja.es

²Dept. of Informatics, King’s College London, London, UK,
luc.moreau@kcl.ac.uk

1 Introduction

This specification defines in detail the patterns for translating UML into PROV. The main objective of this specification is to provide a tool for implementing systems that include provenance capabilities during their design phase.

This document has been organized into three main parts:

- Section 2 provides an insight into the information required for the accurate understanding of this specification such as the notational conventions used throughout the document (Section 2.1), or the description of the structure for the pattern’s explanations (Section 2.2).
- Section 3 shows a table that associates each pattern’s identifier with the page where it is explained.
- Sections from 4 to 6 provide a systematic explanation of each pattern classified by the addressed UML diagram.

2 Before reading

As we see this document as the reference specification for UML2PROV, each pattern has been written in a self-contained way. A reader who reads all the patterns sequentially from the first to the last will find similar explanations, even repeated ones, in several patterns. We have preferred to make the reader suffer this small inconvenience, instead of running the risk that an occasional reader of a particular pattern loses part of the explanations that are discussed elsewhere.

We assume that the reader is familiar with the following UML diagrams: UML Sequence Diagrams (SqDs), UML State Machine Diagrams (SMDs), and UML Class diagrams (CDs). Readers unfamiliar with these diagrams are encouraged to read the UML specification [1]. Additionally, due to the fact that transformations referring to CDs make use of concrete UML stereotypes used to classify UML Class’s operations, we refer to [Appendix A](#) for an overview about them.

Likewise, we assume that the reader is knowledgeable about both the PROV data model (PROV-DM) [2], to represent provenance information, and the PROV template approach [3], for designing provenance. If this is not the case, she/he is referred to [2] and [3], respectively.

2.1 Notational conventions

More than a terminological nuance, the distinction between the *state* and the *status* of an object is fundamental to understand this document. More specifically:

- In SMDs, in accordance to UML terminology [1], the *state* of an object denotes a situation during which some invariant conditions holds.
- In CDs, we use the term object's *status* with a broad scope, referring to the values of the object's attributes at some moment, which particularly could correspond to a concrete *state* but not necessarily.

The PROV templates throughout this document are represented following the PROV graph conventions given in [4].

We also use *qualified names* (e.g., `prov:value`) in accordance to PROV-DM [2]. In compliance with PROV-DM, we note that a *qualified name* can be mapped to an Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI) [5] by concatenating the IRI associated with the prefix (e.g., `prov`) and the local part (e.g., `value`). Every *qualified name* with a prefix refers to the namespace of the prefix. The following namespaces and prefixes are used throughout this document.

prefix	namespace IRI	definition
var	http://openprovenance.org/var#	The namespace for template variables
prov	http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#	The PROV namespace
xsd	http://www.w3.org/2000/10/XMLSchema#	XML Schema namespace
u2p	http://uml2prov.unirioja.es/ns/u2p#	UML2PROV namespace

Table 1. Prefix and Namespaces used in this specification

2.2 Structure of the patterns

We have structured the explanation of the defined patterns in the same five blocks: **Identifier**, **Context**, **UML Diagram**, **Mapping to PROV**, and **Discussion**. See the explanation of each block below.

2.2.1 Identifier

Unique identifier of the transformation pattern. It is an acronym that refers to the type of UML diagram together with a numeric identifier. The UML *Sequence diagram Patterns* are referred to as *SeqP<N>*, where *N* is the numeric identifier. Likewise, *StP<N>* corresponds to the UML *State Machine Patterns*, and *CIP<N>* to the UML *Class Diagram Patterns*.

2.2.2 Context

The behaviour addressed by the pattern. In order to give a free of context explanation, being as agnostic as possible about the modeling language used to represent such a behaviour, we will use the natural language including well-known software engineering terminology (e.g., *object*, *operation*...), to identify the part of the domain for which the corresponding pattern proposes a translation.

Each pattern context block will include a detailed description of its *key elements*. When necessary, we will use nested elements to describe the different alternatives through which certain *key elements* participate in the context. We remark that not all the identified *key elements* explicitly appear in the context. Some patterns identify specific *key elements* that are inferred from the context because they play an important role in the pattern.

2.2.3 UML Diagram

This block will depict the excerpt of the UML diagram with the elements that model the previous *key elements*. In addition, we provide a table, whose structure is illustrated below, that explains the representation of each *key element*, by means of UML elements. Additionally, we assign a green label containing a numeric identifier to each UML element, which makes it easier its location in the UML diagram.

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Name of the element</i>	UML element	The fundamental reasons serving to account for the use of the <i>UML element</i> for modelling the <i>key element</i> .

2.2.4 Mapping to PROV

This block contains the PROV template generated from the previous excerpt of *UML Diagram*, together with an explanation about the transformation, that is, the *PROV elements*, *attributes*, and *PROV relations* generated from the UML elements in the *UML Diagram*. We assign a numeric identifier to each *PROV element* that corresponds to the identifier of the *UML element* from which it comes from. Additionally, each *relation* among PROV elements appearing in the PROV template is labeled with a letter that helps link such a relation with its description. The structure used to specify this block is the following:

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
UML element / var:<identifier>	The explanation of the mapping between <i>UML element</i> and <i>PROV element</i> .	

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
PROV element	name of attribute / assigned value	The description of the meaning of the attribute and its value.

Note: Throughout this specification, we have included the attributes `tmpl:startTime` and `tmpl:endTime` associated with `Activities` because we consider such an information very useful from a provenance point of view. Nevertheless, both attributes are optional and the user is free to include them.

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
PROV relation	Description of the relation.

Note: In PROV, two relationships of the form (B, `prov:used`, A) and (C, `prov:wasGeneratedBy`, B) may be enriched with (C, `prov:wasDerivedFrom`, A) to express the dependency of C on A. This structure is a provenance construction called *use-generate-derive triangle* [3] which explicitly connects a *generated* `prov:Entity` to a *used* `prov:Entity`. In the realm of this work, it may be applied in those templates in which a `prov:Entity` is *used* by a `prov:Activity`, and such a `prov:Activity` *generated* another `prov:Entity`. However, aiming at avoiding the overburden of the PROV template explanations with information that can be inferred, we have decided to include the relation `prov:wasDerivedFrom` only when the context of the pattern explicitly refers to such a derivation.

2.2.5 Discussion

Issues related to the transformation of UML to PROV. Concretely, we will focus on the explanation and justification of our transformation decisions together with alternative solutions (if any), and some questions that are likely to come up to the reader.

3 Index of patterns

Modelled by means of UML Sequence Diagrams

Pattern identifier	Context	Page
SeqP1	A participant (the sender) interacts with another participant (the recipient) by calling an operation in the recipient, and then, it continues immediately. The call causes the recipient to execute the operation.	6
SeqP2	A participant (the sender) interacts with another participant (the recipient) by calling an operation in the recipient and waiting for a response. The call causes the recipient to execute the operation and to respond the sender after the execution.	9
SeqP3	During the execution of an operation (main operation), a nested operation call is made. After this call, the execution of the main operation can either continue immediately or wait for the response of that nested operation call. This way, this pattern complements SeqP1 and SeqP2 .	12
SeqP4	During the execution of an operation (main operation), a response of a previously issued nested operation call is received. The main operation's execution uses this response to complete its behaviour. This way, this pattern complements SeqP1 and SeqP2 with additional information regarding the response to the <i>nested operation call</i> (addressed by SeqP3).	15

Modelled by means of UML State Machine Diagrams

Pattern identifier	Context	Page
StP1	As a consequence of the execution of an operation, an object is created in its first state. This operation is usually the constructor of the object.	19
StP2	As a consequence of the execution of an operation, the behaviour of an object is completed.	23
StP3	As a consequence of the execution of an operation, an object changes its state.	27

Modelled by means of UML Class Diagrams

Pattern identifier	Context	Page
CIP1	The execution of an operation provokes the creation of a new object.	33
CIP2	The execution of an operation provokes the destruction of an object.	36
CIP3	The execution of an operation on an object returns values of concrete object's attributes. The values are returned as they are, without any further processing. This execution does not provoke the change of the object's status.	38
CIP4	The execution of an operation on an object returns values that are computed based on the object's status as a whole (the values of concrete attributes involved in the computation are unknown or irrelevant). This execution does not provoke the change of the object's status.	41
CIP5	The execution of an operation on an object returns values that are computed based on values of concrete object's attributes. This execution does not provoke the change of the object's status.	44
CIP6	The execution of an operation on an object changes the object's status as a whole (the concrete modified attributes are unknown or irrelevant).	48
CIP7	The execution of an operation on an object directly sets the information passed to the operation as values of concrete object's attributes, thus provoking a change in the object's status.	53
CIP8	The execution of an operation on an object changes the values of concrete object's attributes, thus provoking a change in the object's status.	58
CIP9	The execution of an operation on an object removes element(s) from a concrete object's collection attribute, thus provoking a change in the object's status.	63
CIP10	The execution of an operation on an object directly adds the information passed to the operation as new element(s) of a concrete object's collection attribute, thus provoking a change in the object's status.	68

4 UML Sequence Diagrams

Pattern identifier	Context	Page
SeqP1	A participant (the sender) interacts with another participant (the recipient) by calling an operation in the recipient, and then, it continues immediately. The call causes the recipient to execute the operation.	6
SeqP2	A participant (the sender) interacts with another participant (the recipient) by calling an operation in the recipient and waiting for a response. The call causes the recipient to execute the operation and to respond the sender after the execution.	9
SeqP3	During the execution of an operation (main operation), a nested operation call is made. After this call, the execution of the main operation can either continue immediately or wait for the response of that nested operation call. This way, this pattern complements SeqP1 and SeqP2 .	12
SeqP4	During the execution of an operation (main operation), a response of a previously issued nested operation call is received. The main operation's execution uses this response to complete its behaviour. This way, this pattern complements SeqP1 and SeqP2 with additional information regarding the response to the <i>nested operation call</i> (addressed by SeqP3).	15

Identifier *Sequence diagram Pattern 1 (SeqPI)*

Context

A participant (the sender) interacts with another participant (the recipient) by calling an operation in the recipient, and then, it continues immediately. The call causes the recipient to execute the operation.

Key elements

- Sender* The participant that makes the operation call.
- Operation call* The call that starts the execution of the operation.
- Input data* The information (if any) passed to the operation through the *Operation call*.
- Operation execution* The execution of the operation.

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Sender</i>	Lifeline 1	It models the <i>Sender</i> participant involved in the interaction.
<i>Operation call</i>	Asynchronous Message	It models the <i>Operation call</i> when the <i>Sender</i> does not wait for a response, but instead continues immediately after sending the message.
<i>Input data</i>	Input Arguments	They specify the information passed to the operation through the <i>Operation call</i> .
<i>Operation execution</i>	ExecutionSpecification	It shows the period of time that the recipient's participant devotes to the <i>Operation execution</i> .

Figure 1. UML representation that models the context given by *SeqPI*

Mapping to PROV

Figure 2. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in *SeqPI* (Figure 1)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Lifeline 1	<code>prov:Agent</code> 1 / <code>var:senderObject</code>	The sender Lifeline 1 is mapped to a <code>prov:Agent</code> identified by <code>var:senderObject</code> . It assumes the responsibility for starting the <code>ExecutionSpecification</code> 4.
Asynchronous Message 2	<code>prov:Entity</code> 2 / <code>var:starter</code>	The Asynchronous Message 2 that initiates the <code>ExecutionSpecification</code> 4 of the recipient is a <code>prov:Entity</code> with identifier <code>var:starter</code> .
Input Arguments 3	<code>prov:Entity</code> 3 / <code>var:input</code>	Each argument of Input Arguments 3 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:input</code> .
<code>ExecutionSpecification</code> 4	<code>prov:Activity</code> 4 / <code>var:operation</code>	The <code>ExecutionSpecification</code> 4 is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with identifier <code>var:operation</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
<code>var:senderObject</code> 1	<code>u2p:typeName</code> / <code>var:className</code>	The value <code>var:className</code> is the string with the name of the class to which the <code>var:senderObject</code> 1 belongs.
<code>var:starter</code> 2	<code>prov:type</code> / <code>u2p:RequestMessage</code>	The value <code>u2p:RequestMessage</code> shows that <code>var:starter</code> 2 is a request message.
<code>var:input</code> 3	<code>prov:value</code> / <code>var:inputValue</code> <code>u2p:typeName</code> / <code>var:inputType</code>	The value <code>var:inputValue</code> is the direct representation of <code>var:input</code> 3. The value <code>var:inputType</code> is the string with the name of the class to which <code>var:input</code> 3 belongs.
<code>var:operation</code> 4	<code>prov:type</code> / <code>var:operationName</code> <code>tmpl:startTime</code> / <code>var:operationStartTime</code> <code>tmpl:endTime</code> / <code>var:operationEndTime</code>	The value <code>var:operationName</code> is the name of the operation <code>var:operation</code> 4. <code>var:operationStartTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the start of <code>var:operation</code> 4. <code>var:operationEndTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the end of <code>var:operation</code> 4.

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:input</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:starter</code> .
b <code>prov:wasStartedBy</code>	<code>var:operation</code> is deemed to have been started by <code>var:starter</code> .
c <code>prov:wasAssociatedWith</code>	It is the assignment of responsibility to <code>var:senderObject</code> for <code>var:operation</code> .
d <code>prov:used</code>	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:starter</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .

Discussion

- Figure 2 depicts the responsibility of the *Sender* lifeline (`var:senderObject`) for the recipient lifeline to execute the operation (`var:operation`). However, the recipient lifeline is not modelled in this PROV template, even though it is the participant that executes the operation. This decision is based on other patterns' better ability to both (1) identify the participant responsible for executing that operation, and (2) give a more detailed information about the implications that the execution of that operation has in the recipient participant. More specifically, these patterns are: *StP1-StP3*, which mainly focus on representing possible changes in an object's state caused by an *Operation execution*; and patterns *CIP1-CIP10*, which put more stress on how the execution affects the status of the object responsible for performing such an execution.
- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that *Input data* should be passed to the operation, we have considered this circumstance with the aim of covering a wider spectrum of cases. When the *Operation call* lacks *Input*

data, the UML representation in Figure 1 will not include Input Arguments ③. As a consequence, the resulting PROV template in Figure 2 will also lack `var:input` ③ and its associated PROV relations. Finally, we remark that the resulting PROV template does not reflect the *usage* of `var:input` ③ by `var:operation` ④ because SqDs stick to the flow of information, not its usage. Patterns addressing CDs (*CIP1-CIP10*) are better suited for this purpose.

Identifier *Sequence diagram Pattern 2 (SeqP2)*

Context

A participant (the sender) interacts with another participant (the recipient) by calling an operation in the recipient and waiting for a response. The call causes the recipient to execute the operation and to respond the sender after the execution.

Key elements

<i>Sender</i>	The participant that makes the operation call.
<i>Operation call</i>	The call that starts the execution of the operation.
<i>Input data</i>	The information (if any) passed to the operation through the <i>Operation call</i> .
<i>Operation execution</i>	The execution of the operation.
<i>Response</i>	The recipient's response to the <i>Operation call</i> .
<i>Output data</i>	The information contained in the <i>Response</i> .

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Sender</i>	Lifeline 1	It models the <i>Sender</i> participant involved in the interaction.
<i>Operation call</i>	Synchronous Message 2	It models the <i>Operation call</i> when the <i>Sender</i> waits for a response.
<i>Input data</i>	Input Arguments 3	They specify the information passed to the operation through the <i>Operation call</i> .
<i>Operation execution</i>	ExecutionSpecification 4	It shows the period of time that the recipient's participant devotes to the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Response</i>	Reply Message 5	It specifies the response to the <i>Operation call</i> .
<i>Output data</i>	Output Arguments 6	They specify the information contained in the <i>Response</i> .

Figure 3. UML representation that models the context given by *SeqP2*

Mapping to PROV

Figure 4. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in *SeqP2* (Figure 3)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Lifeline 1	<code>prov:Agent</code> 1 / <code>var:senderObject</code>	The sender Lifeline 1 is mapped to a <code>prov:Agent</code> identified by <code>var:senderObject</code> . It assumes the responsibility for starting the <code>ExecutionSpecification</code> 4.
Synchronous Message 2	<code>prov:Entity</code> 2 / <code>var:starter</code>	The Synchronous Message 2 that initiates the <code>ExecutionSpecification</code> 4 of the recipient is a <code>prov:Entity</code> with identifier <code>var:starter</code> .
Input Arguments 3	<code>prov:Entity</code> 3 / <code>var:input</code>	Each argument of Input Arguments 3 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:input</code> .
<code>ExecutionSpecification</code> 4	<code>prov:Activity</code> 4 / <code>var:operation</code>	The <code>ExecutionSpecification</code> 4 is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with identifier <code>var:operation</code> .
Reply Message 5	<code>prov:Entity</code> 5 / <code>var:response</code>	The Reply Message 5 that responds to the Synchronous Message 2 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> with identifier <code>var:response</code> .
Output Arguments 6	<code>prov:Entity</code> 6 / <code>var:output</code>	Each argument of Output Arguments 6 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:output</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:senderObject belongs.		
var:starter is a request message.		
var:input .		
	u2p:typeName / var:inputType	The value var:inputType is the string with the name of the class to which the var:input belongs.
var:operation .		
	tmpl:startTime / var:operationStartTime	The var:operationStartTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of var:operation .
	tmpl:endTime / var:operationEndTime	The var:operationEndTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of var:operation .
var:response is a reply message.		
var:output .		
	u2p:typeName / var:outputType	The value var:outputType is a string with the name of the class to which var:output belongs.

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
prov:hadMember	It states that var:input is one of the elements in var:starter.
prov:wasStartedBy	var:operation is deemed to have been started by var:starter.
prov:wasAssociatedWith	It is the assignment of responsibility to var:senderObject for var:operation.
prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:response by var:operation.
prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:response based on var:starter reception.
prov:hadMember	It states that var:output is one of the elements in var:response.
prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:starter by var:operation.

Discussion

- Figure 4 depicts the responsibility of the *Sender* lifeline (var:senderObject) for executing the operation (var:operation) in a recipient lifeline. However, the recipient lifeline is not modelled in this PROV template, even though it is the participant that executes the operation. This decision is based on other patterns' better ability to both (1) identify the participant responsible for executing that operation, and (2) give a more detailed information about the implications that the execution of that operation has in the recipient participant. More specifically, these patterns are: *StP1-StP3*, which mainly focus on representing possible changes in an object's state caused by an *Operation execution*; and patterns *CIP1-CIP10*, which put more stress on how the execution affects the status of the object responsible for performing such an execution.
- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that *Input data* should be passed to the operation, we have considered this circumstance with the aim of covering a wider spectrum of cases. When the *Operation call* lacks *Input data*, the UML representation in Figure 3 will not include *Input Arguments* because SqDs stick to the flow of information, not its usage. Patterns addressing CDs (*CIP1-CIP10*) are better suited for this purpose.

Identifier Sequence diagram Pattern 3 (*SeqP3*)

Context

During the execution of an operation (main operation), a nested operation call is made. After this call, the execution of the main operation can either continue immediately or wait for the response of that nested operation call. This way, this pattern complements *SeqP1* and *SeqP2*.

Key elements

- (Main) Operation execution The execution of the main operation.
- (Nested) Operation call The nested operation call sent during the *Main operation execution*.

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Main operation execution</i>	ExecutionSpecification 1	It shows the period of time that takes the <i>Main operation execution</i> .
<i>Nested operation call</i>	Synchronous Message 2 or Asynchronous Message 2	It models the <i>Nested operation call</i> either when its sender waits for a response, or when it does not wait for a response, but instead continues immediately after sending the message.

Figure 5. The left hand side is the UML representation of *SeqP1* complemented by *SeqP3*, whereas the right hand side is the UML representation of *SeqP2* complemented by *SeqP3*. Only the shaded areas correspond to the UML elements contributed by this pattern.

Mapping to PROV

Figure 6. At the top, it is a PROV template generated from the UML representation in the left side of Figure 5. At the bottom, it is a PROV template generated from the UML representation in the right side of Figure 5. Only the shaded areas correspond to the PROV elements contributed by this pattern.

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
ExecutionSpecification 1	<code>prov:Activity</code> 1 / <code>var:operation</code>	The ExecutionSpecification 1 is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with identifier <code>var:operation</code> .
Synchronous Message 2 or Asynchronous Message 2	<code>prov:Entity</code> 2 / <code>var:nestedRequest</code>	The Synchronous Message or Asynchronous Message 2 sent from the ExecutionSpecification 1 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> with identifier <code>var:nestedRequest</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:operation 1	prov:type /	The value var:operationName is the name of the operation var:operation 1 .
	var:operationName	
	tmpl:startTime /	The var:operationStartTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of var:operation 4 .
	var:operationStartTime	
tmpl:endTime /	The var:operationEndTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of var:operation 4 .	
var:operationEndTime		
var:nestedRequest 2	prov:type / u2p:RequestMessage	The value u2p:RequestMessage shows that var:nestedRequest 5 is a request message.

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:nestedRequest by var:operation.

Discussion

- The same element ('request message' in this case) appears in different patterns playing different roles. In [SeqP3](#) the request message models the call started from an ExecutionSpecification. However, in [SeqP1](#) and [SeqP2](#), this same request message models the call that starts an ExecutionSpecification. The former way of looking at the request message is translated into var:nestedRequest (in [SeqP3](#)), and the latter is translated into var:starter (in [SeqP1](#) and [SeqP2](#)). Consequently, despite var:nestedRequest and var:starter being two different elements of type prov:Entity appearing in two different PROV templates, both must be assigned to the same value during the execution of the application. Therefore, after merging all the expanded PROV templates, a single prov:Entity will be generated.

Identifier *Sequence diagram Pattern 4 (SeqP4)*

Context

During the execution of an operation (main operation), a response of a previously issued nested operation call is received. The main operation’s execution uses this response to complete its behaviour. This way, this pattern complements *SeqP1* and *SeqP2* with additional information regarding the response to the *nested operation call* (addressed by *SeqP3*).

Key elements

- (Main) *Operation execution* The execution of the main operation.
- (Nested) *Response* The response to a nested operation call.
- (Main) *Response* The response of the *Main operation execution*. This element is only identified when this pattern complements *SeqP2*.

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Main operation execution</i>	ExecutionSpecification 1	It shows the period of time that takes the <i>Main operation execution</i> .
<i>Nested response</i>	Reply Message 2	It specifies the response received in the <i>Main operation execution</i> .
<i>Main response</i>	Reply Message 3	In case of complementing <i>SeqP2</i> , it specifies the response of the <i>Main operation execution</i> .

Figure 7. The left hand side is the UML representation that models the context given by *SeqP1* complemented by *SeqP4*, whereas the right hand side is the UML representation that models the context given by *SeqP2* complemented by *SeqP4*. Only the shaded areas correspond to the UML elements contributed by this pattern.

Mapping to PROV

Figure 8. At the top, it is the PROV template generated from the UML representation in the left side of Figure 7. At the bottom, it is a PROV template generated from the UML representation in the right side of Figure 7. Only the shaded areas correspond to the PROV elements contributed by this pattern.

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
ExecutionSpecification 1	prov:Activity 1 / <code>var:operation</code>	The ExecutionSpecification 1 is a prov:Activity with identifier <code>var:operation</code> .
Reply Message 2	prov:Entity 2 / <code>var:nestedResponse</code>	The Reply Message 2 that is received in the ExecutionSpecification 1 is a prov:Entity with identifier <code>var:nestedResponse</code> .
Reply Message 3	prov:Entity 3 / <code>var:response</code>	In case of complementing <i>SeqP2</i> , the Reply Message 3 sent from the ExecutionSpecification 1 is a prov:Entity with identifier <code>var:response</code> . For details, see <i>SeqP2</i> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
<code>var:operation</code> 1	prov:type / <code>var:operationName</code>	The value <code>var:operationName</code> is the name of the operation <code>var:operation</code> 1 .
	tmpl:startTime / <code>var:operationStartTime</code>	The <code>var:operationStartTime</code> is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of <code>var:operation</code> 1 .
	tmpl:endTime / <code>var:operationEndTime</code>	The <code>var:operationEndTime</code> is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of <code>var:operation</code> 1 .
<code>var:nestedResponse</code> 2	prov:type / u2p:ReplyMessage	The value u2p:ReplyMessage shows that <code>var:response</code> 2 is a reply message.
<code>var:response</code> 3	prov:type / u2p:ReplyMessage	The value u2p:ReplyMessage shows that <code>var:response</code> 3 is a reply message.

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:nestedResponse</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
b prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of <code>var:response</code> based on <code>var:nestedResponse</code> .

Discussion

- As it could be inferred from the context, a requirement for this pattern to be applied is that the *Main operation execution* uses the *Nested response* during its execution. This causes the relations **a** [prov:used](#) and **b** [prov:wasDerivedFrom](#) to appear in the template; the former showing that when the ExecutionSpecification **1** receives the nested Reply Message **2**, it *utilises* that Reply Message **2** to complete its behaviour; and the latter showing that the main Reply Message **3** is *influenced* by the nested Reply Message **2** (this last one can only be applied if the *Main operation execution* is triggered by a synchronous message, i.e. when *SeqP4* complements *SeqP2*). If a specific scenario does not meet the aforementioned requirement, i.e., the *Main operation execution* does not use the *Nested response* or it is not worth recording such a dependency, this pattern should not be applied. Even in this case, the provenance about the nested operation call and its corresponding response would be captured thanks to *SeqP1* and *SeqP2*, respectively.

5 UML State Machine Diagrams

Pattern identifier	Context	Page
StP1	As a consequence of the execution of an operation, an object is created in its first state. This operation is usually the constructor of the object.	19
StP2	As a consequence of the execution of an operation, the behaviour of an object is completed.	23
StP3	As a consequence of the execution of an operation, an object changes its state.	27

Identifier *State machine diagram Pattern 1 (StPI)*

Context

As a consequence of the execution of an operation, an object is created in its first state. This operation is usually the constructor of the object.

Key elements

- Object** The object created as a consequence of the execution of the operation.
- First object's state** The first state after the object creation. This is the first state the object may undergo during its lifetime.
- Object creation** The execution of the operation that creates the object.

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
Object	Object 1	It represents the created object. <i>Note:</i> since <code>Object</code> lacks a graphical representation in UML State Machine diagrams, Figure 9 does not depict this element.
	StateMachine 2	In UML, a <code>StateMachine</code> represents the set of states an <i>Object</i> can go through during its lifetime in response to events.
Object creation	Initial Pseudostate 3	It refers to the execution of the operation that creates the <i>Object</i> , leading it to its first state.
	State 4	It models the first state of the <i>Object</i> .

Figure 9. UML representation that models the context given by *StPI*

Mapping to PROV

Figure 10. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in *StPI* (Figure 9)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Object 1	<code>prov:Agent 1 /</code> <code>var:object</code>	The Object 1 bears some form of responsibility for the existence of the StateMachine 2, since the existence of StateMachine 2 does not make sense without an Object 1. To reflect this fact, the Object 1 is mapped to a <code>prov:Agent</code> identified by <code>var:object</code> .
StateMachine 2	<code>prov:Entity 2 /</code> <code>var:objectSM</code>	The StateMachine 2 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:objectSM</code> . It reflects the abstraction of the object's states, which will be specialized by each concrete state the object goes through.
Initial Pseudostate 3	<code>prov:Activity 3 /</code> <code>var:operation</code>	The Initial Pseudostate 3, referring to the execution of the operation that creates the Object 1, is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:operation</code> .
State 4	<code>prov:Entity 4 /</code> <code>var:postObject</code>	The State 4 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:postObject</code> . We use this name for this identifier because it corresponds to the state of the Object 1 after (post) the object creation.

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
<code>var:object 1</code>	<code>u2p:typeName /</code> <code>var:className</code>	The value <code>var:className</code> is the string with the name of the class to which <code>var:object 1</code> belongs.
<code>var:objectSM 2</code>	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>u2p:StateMachine</code>	The value <code>u2p:StateMachine</code> shows that <code>var:objectSM 2</code> is a state machine.
<code>var:operation 3</code>	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>var:operationName</code>	The value <code>var:operationName</code> is the name of the operation <code>var:operation 3</code> .
	<code>tmpl:startTime /</code> <code>var:operationStartTime</code>	The <code>var:operationStartTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the start of <code>var:operation 3</code> .
	<code>tmpl:endTime /</code> <code>var:operationEndTime</code>	The <code>var:operationEndTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the end of <code>var:operation 3</code> .
<code>var:postObject 4</code>	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>var:className</code>	The value <code>var:className</code> is the name of the class to which the object in the state <code>var:postObject 4</code> belongs.
	<code>u2p:state /</code> <code>var:targetState</code>	The value <code>var:targetState</code> is the string with the name of the state <code>var:postObject 4</code> .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a <code>prov:wasAttributedTo</code>	It is the assignment of responsibility to <code>var:object</code> for <code>var:objectSM</code> .
b <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:postObject</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
c <code>prov:specializationOf</code>	<code>var:postObject</code> is a specialization of <code>var:objectSM</code> .

Discussion

- Note that Figure 9 only contains simple states. We do not deal with composite or submachine states, and focus only on simple states, because the former may be transformed into the latter by resorting to a flattening process consisting of removing composite states as well as submachine states. In fact, to flatten State Machine diagrams is a very common approach in contexts such as model checking and code generation [6]. However, the user might be interested in representing composite states directly into the PROV templates, perhaps because she/he is interested in collecting information about them, or just because she/he does not want to flatten the State Machine diagram. We can give an insight into how composite states can be mapped to PROV by placing the elements from Figure 9 inside a Composite State 5 (see Figure 11). A reader familiar with the UML specification will realize that the semantics of the Initial Pseudostate 3 in Figures 9 and 11

are different, but these semantic nuances would have no effect on the PROV transformation. The transformation of Figure 11 is shown in Figure 12. Both Figure 11 and 12 highlight the added elements by blurring the elements coming from Figure 9 and Figure 10, respectively. Briefly speaking, the new Composite State 5 is translated into a `prov:Entity` identified by `var:compState` 5, which is associated with `var:objectSM` 2 and `var:targetState` 4 by means of the relations 1 `prov:specializationOf` and 3 `prov:hadMember`, respectively. At this point, it is also worth remarking that for this example we have used a *simple composite state* (i.e., Composite State 5), which means that only one substate is active at a given time within such a state; but we could have used *orthogonal composite states* instead, which means that within such a state several substates are active at the same time. Note that both types of *composite states* would be translated into the same PROV template (see Figure 12); nevertheless, the generated bindings would be different. In case of a *simple composite state*, as there can be only one active substate at the same time, there would be only one value associated with the variable `var:postObject` 4. Conversely, in case of an *orthogonal composite state*, `var:postObject` 4 will be associated with several values (as many as active states).

Figure 11. Excerpt of a UML State Machine diagram locating the UML elements from *StPI* in a *simple composite state*.

Figure 12. PROV template generated from the UML diagram in Figure 11

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Composite State 5	<code>prov:Entity</code> 5 / <code>var:compState</code>	The Composite State 5 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:compState</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
<code>var:compState</code> 5	<code>u2p:state</code> / <code>var:compStateName</code>	The value <code>var:compStateName</code> is the string with the name of the state <code>var:compState</code> 5

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
prov:specializationOf	<code>var:compState</code> is a specialization of <code>var:objectSM</code> .
prov:hadMember	It states that <code>var:postObject</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:compState</code> .

Identifier State machine diagram Pattern 2 (StP2)

Context

As a consequence of the execution of an operation, the behaviour of an object is completed.

Key elements

- Object* The object that completes its behaviour.
- Pre-operation object's state* The state of the object before the execution of the operation. This is one of the states the object may undergo during its lifetime.
- Final object's state* The state that represents that the object's behaviour is completed.
- Operation execution* The execution of the operation that leads the object to complete its behaviour.

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Object</i>	Object 1	It represents the object whose behaviour is completed. <i>Note:</i> since <i>Object</i> lacks a graphical representation in UML State Machine diagrams, Figure 13 does not depict this element.
	State Machine 2	In UML, a <i>State Machine</i> can be used to express the set of states through which the <i>Object</i> goes during its lifetime in response to events.
<i>Pre-operation object's state</i>	State 3	It models the state of the <i>Object</i> before the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Final object's state</i>	Final State 4	It models the state of the <i>Object</i> after the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Operation execution</i>	Event 5	It specifies that the <i>Operation execution</i> that triggers the change in the <i>Object's</i> state has taken place.

Figure 13. UML representation that models the context given by StP2

Mapping to PROV

Figure 14. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in StP2 (Figure 13)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Object 1	<code>prov:Agent 1 /</code> <code>var:object</code>	The Object 1 bears some form of responsibility for the existence of the StateMachine 2, since the existence of StateMachine 2 does not make sense without an Object 1. To reflect this fact, the Object 1 is mapped to a <code>prov:Agent</code> identified by <code>var:object</code> .
StateMachine 2	<code>prov:Entity 2 /</code> <code>var:objectSM</code>	The StateMachine 2 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:objectSM</code> . It reflects the abstraction of the object's states, which will be specialized by each state the object goes through.
State 3	<code>prov:Entity 3 /</code> <code>var:preObject</code>	The State 3 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:preObject</code> . We use this name for this identifier because it corresponds to the state of the Object 1 before (pre) the execution of the operation.
FinalState 4	None /	Without mapping (see the discussion block for an explanation about this decision).
Event 5	<code>prov:Activity 5 /</code> <code>var:operation</code>	The Event 5 represents that the execution of an operation has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:operation</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
<code>var:object 1</code>	<code>u2p:typeName /</code> <code>var:className</code>	The value <code>var:className</code> is the string with the name of the class to which <code>var:object 1</code> belongs.
<code>var:objectSM 2</code>	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>u2p:StateMachine</code>	The value <code>u2p:StateMachine</code> shows that <code>var:objectSM 2</code> is a state machine.
<code>var:preObject 3</code>	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>var:className</code>	The value <code>var:className</code> is the string with the name of the class to which the object in the state <code>var:preObject 3</code> belongs.
	<code>u2p:state /</code> <code>var:sourceState</code>	The value <code>var:sourceState</code> is the string with the name of the state <code>var:preObject 3</code> .
<code>var:operation 5</code>	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>var:operationName</code>	The value <code>var:operationName</code> is the name of the operation <code>var:operation 5</code> .
	<code>tmpl:startTime /</code> <code>var:operationStartTime</code>	The <code>var:operationStartTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the start of <code>var:operation 5</code> .
	<code>tmpl:endTime /</code> <code>var:operationEndTime</code>	The <code>var:operationEndTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the end of <code>var:operation 5</code> .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a <code>prov:wasAttributedTo</code>	It is the assignment of responsibility to <code>var:object</code> for <code>var:objectSM</code> .
b <code>prov:used</code>	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:preObject</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
c <code>prov:wasInvalidatedBy</code>	It shows that <code>var:preObject</code> is not longer available for use.
d <code>prov:specializationOf</code>	<code>var:preObject</code> is a specialization of <code>var:objectSM</code> .

Discussion

- This pattern is consistent with *CIP2* because the completion of the object's behaviour usually involves its destruction. Among the different reasons why an *Object* can complete its behaviour, we can distinguish its destruction, from the remainder cases. In order to be consistent with *CIP2* (that addresses the execution of an operation which provokes the destruction of an object), we have decided not to explicitly map the `FinalState 4` in the PROV template but including its semantics (the completion of the object's behaviour) by the relation **c** `prov:wasInvalidatedBy` showing that `var:preObject 3` is not longer

available. However, if the user is interested in explicitly representing the `FinalState` 4 into the PROV templates, we refer him/her to *StP3*, where the state of the *Object* before and after an *Operation execution* is included.

- Figure 13 only contains simple states. We do not deal with composite or submachine states, and focus only on simple states, because the former may be transformed into the latter by resorting to a flattening process consisting of removing composite states as well as submachine states. In fact, to flatten State Machine diagrams is a very common approach in contexts such as model checking and code generation [6]. However, the user might be interested in representing composite states directly into the PROV templates, perhaps because she/he is interested in collecting information about them, or just because she/he does not want to flatten the State Machine diagram. We can give an insight into how composite states can be mapped to PROV by placing the elements from Figure 13 inside a `Composite State` 5 (see Figure 15). A reader familiar with the UML specification will realize that the semantics of the `FinalState` 4 in Figures 13 and 15 are different, but these semantic nuances would have no effect on the PROV transformation. The transformation of Figure 15 is shown in Figure 16. Both Figure 15 and 16 highlight the added elements by blurring the elements coming from Figure 13 and Figure 14, respectively. Briefly speaking, the new `Composite State` 6 is translated into a `prov:Entity` identified by `var:compState` 6, which is associated with `var:objectSM` 2 and `var:preObject` 3 by means of the relations `prov:specializationOf` 1 and `prov:hadMember` 3, respectively. At this point, it is also worth remarking that for this example we have used a *simple composite state* (i.e., `Composite State` 5), which means that only one substate is active at a given time within such a state; but we could have used *orthogonal composite states* instead, which means that within such a state several substates are active at the same time. Note that both types of *composite states* would be translated into the same PROV template (see Figure 16); nevertheless, the generated bindings would be different. In case of a *simple composite state*, as there can be only one active substate at the same time, there would be only one value associated with the variable `var:preObject` 3. Conversely, in case of an *orthogonal composite state*, `var:preObject` 3 will be associated with several values (as many as active states).

Figure 15. Excerpt of a UML State Machine diagram locating the UML elements from *StP2* in a *simple composite state*.

Figure 16. PROV template generated from the UML diagram in Figure 15

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Composite State 6	<code>prov:Entity</code> 6 / <code>var:compState</code>	The Composite State 6 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:compState</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
<code>var:compState</code>		

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
<code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:preObject</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:compState</code> .
<code>prov:specializationOf</code>	<code>var:compState</code> is a specialization of <code>var:objectSM</code> .

Identifier State machine diagram Pattern 3 (*StP3*)

Context

As a consequence of the execution of an operation, an object changes its state.

Key elements

<i>Object</i>	The object that changes its state.
<i>Pre-operation object's state</i>	The state of the object before the execution of the operation. This is one of the states the object may undergo during its lifetime.
<i>Post-operation object's state</i>	The state of the object after the execution of the operation. This is one of the states the object may undergo during its lifetime.
<i>Operation execution</i>	The execution of the operation that leads a change in the <i>Object's</i> state.

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Object</i>	Object 1	It represents the object that changes its state. <i>Note:</i> since <i>Object</i> lacks a graphical representation in UML State Machine diagrams, Figure 17 does not depict this element.
	StateMachine 2	In UML, a <i>StateMachine</i> can be used to express the set of object's states through which the <i>Object</i> goes during its lifetime in response to events.
<i>Pre-operation object's state</i>	State 3	It models the state of the <i>Object</i> before the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Post-operation object's state</i>	State 4	It models the state of the <i>Object</i> after the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Operation execution</i>	Event 5	It specifies that the <i>Operation execution</i> that triggers the change in the <i>Object's</i> state has taken place.

Figure 17. UML representation that models the context given by *StP3*

Mapping to PROV

Figure 18. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in *StP3* (Figure 17)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Object 1	<code>prov:Agent 1 /</code> <code>var:object</code>	The Object 1 bears some form of responsibility for the existence of the StateMachine 2, since the existence of StateMachine 2 does not make sense without an Object 1. To reflect this fact, the Object 1 is mapped to a <code>prov:Agent</code> identified by <code>var:object</code> .
StateMachine 2	<code>prov:Entity 2 /</code> <code>var:objectSM</code>	The StateMachine 2 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:objectSM</code> . It reflects the abstraction of the object's states, which will be specialized by each state the object goes through.
State 3	<code>prov:Entity 3 /</code> <code>var:preObject</code>	The State 3 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:preObject</code> . We use this name for this identifier because it corresponds to the state of the Object 1 before (pre) the execution of the operation.
State 4	<code>prov:Entity 4 /</code> <code>var:postObject</code>	The State 4 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:postObject</code> . We use this name for this identifier because it corresponds to the state of the Object 1 after (post) the execution of the operation.
Event 5	<code>prov:Activity 5 /</code> <code>var:operation</code>	The Event 5 represents that the execution of an operation has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:operation</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:object 1▶	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the string with the name of the class to which var:object 1▶ belongs.
var:objectSM 2▶	prov:type / u2p:StateMachine	The value u2p:StateMachine shows that var:objectSM 2▶ is a state machine.
var:preObject 3▶	prov:type / var:className u2p:state / var:sourceState	The value var:className is the name of the class to which the object in the state var:preObject 3▶ belongs. The value var:sourceState is the string with the name of the state var:preObject 3▶.
var:postObject 4▶	prov:type / var:className u2p:state / var:targetState	The value var:className is the name of the class to which the object in the state var:postObject 4▶ belongs. The value var:targetState is the string with the name of the state var:postObject 4▶.
var:operation 5▶	prov:type / var:operationName tmpl:startTime / var:operationStartTime tmpl:endTime / var:operationEndTime	The value var:operationName is the name of the operation var:operation 5▶. The var:operationStartTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of var:operation 5▶. The var:operationEndTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of var:operation 5▶.

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:wasAttributedTo	It is the assignment of responsibility to var:object for var:objectSM.
b prov:specializationOf	var:preObject is a specialization of var:objectSM.
c prov:specializationOf	var:postObject is a specialization of var:objectSM.
d prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of var:preObject resulting in var:postObject.
e prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:preObject by var:operation.
f prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:postObject by var:operation.
g prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that var:preObject is not longer available for use.

Discussion

- Figure 17 only contains simple states. We do not deal with composite or submachine states, and focus only on simple states, because the former may be transformed into the latter by resorting to a flattening process consisting of removing composite states as well as submachine states. In fact, to flatten State Machine diagrams is a very common approach in contexts such as model checking and code generation [6]. However, the user might be interested in representing composite states directly into the PROV templates, perhaps because she/he is interested in collecting information about them, or just because she/he does not want to flatten the State Machine diagram. We can give an insight into how composite states can be mapped to PROV by placing the elements from Figure 17 inside a Composite State 5▶ (see Figure 19). A reader familiar with the UML specification will realize that the semantics of the UML representation in Figures 17 and 19 are different, but these semantic nuances would have no effect on the PROV transformation. The transformation of Figure 19 is shown in Figure 20. Both Figure 19 and 20 highlight the added elements by blurring the elements coming from Figure 17 and Figure 18, respectively. Briefly speaking, the new Composite State 5▶ is translated into a prov:Entity identified by var:compState 6▶, which is associated with var:objectSM 2▶, var:preObject 3▶, and var:postObject 4▶ by means of the relations i prov:specializationOf, h prov:hadMember, and i prov:hadMember, respectively. At this point, it is also worth remarking that for this example we have used a *simple composite state* (i.e., Composite State 5▶), which means that only one substate is active at a given time within such a state; but we could have used *orthogonal composite states* instead, which means that within such a state several substates are active at the same time. Note that both types of *composite states* would be translated into the same PROV template (see Figure 20); nevertheless, the generated bindings would be

different. In case of a *simple composite state*, as there can be only one active substate at the same time, there would be only one value associated with the variable `var:preObject` 3 and another value with `var:postObject` 4. Conversely, in case of an *orthogonal composite state*, `var:preObject` 3 and `var:postObject` 4 will be associated with several values (as many as active states).

Figure 19. Excerpt of a UML State Machine diagram locating the UML elements from *StP3* in a *simple composite state*.

Figure 20. PROV template generated from the UML diagram in Figure 19

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Composite State 6	<code>prov:Entity</code> 6 / <code>var:compState</code>	The Composite State 6 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:compState</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
<code>var:compState</code> 6	<code>u2p:state</code> / <code>var:compStateName</code>	The value <code>var:compStateName</code> is the string with the name of the state <code>var:compState</code> 6

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
prov:hadMember	It states that <code>var:preObject</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:compState</code> .
prov:hadMember	It states that <code>var:postObject</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:compState</code> .
prov:specializationOf	<code>var:compState</code> is a specialization of <code>var:objectSM</code> .

6 UML Class Diagrams

Pattern identifier	Context	Page
CIP1	The execution of an operation provokes the creation of a new object.	33
CIP2	The execution of an operation provokes the destruction of an object.	36
CIP3	The execution of an operation on an object returns values of concrete object's attributes. The values are returned as they are, without any further processing. This execution does not provoke the change of the object's status.	38
CIP4	The execution of an operation on an object returns values that are computed based on the object's status as a whole (the values of concrete attributes involved in the computation are unknown or irrelevant). This execution does not provoke the change of the object's status.	41
CIP5	The execution of an operation on an object returns values that are computed based on values of concrete object's attributes. This execution does not provoke the change of the object's status.	44
CIP6	The execution of an operation on an object changes the object's status as a whole (the concrete modified attributes are unknown or irrelevant).	48
CIP7	The execution of an operation on an object directly sets the information passed to the operation as values of concrete object's attributes, thus provoking a change in the object's status.	53
CIP8	The execution of an operation on an object changes the values of concrete object's attributes, thus provoking a change in the object's status.	58
CIP9	The execution of an operation on an object removes element(s) from a concrete object's collection attribute, thus provoking a change in the object's status.	63
CIP10	The execution of an operation on an object directly adds the information passed to the operation as new element(s) of a concrete object's collection attribute, thus provoking a change in the object's status.	68

Identifier Class diagram Pattern 1 (CIP1)

Context

The execution of an operation provokes the creation of a new object.

Key elements

- Object* The object created as a consequence of the execution of the operation.
- Operation execution* The execution of the operation.
- Input data* The information (if any) passed into the *Operation execution*.
- Object's attributes* The characteristics of the *Object*.

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Object</i>	Class 1	<i>Objects</i> are classified attending to their characteristics and behaviour by means of <code>classes</code> . Thus, we use <code>Class 1</code> to represent the <i>Object</i> after the execution of the operation.
<i>Operation execution</i>	Operation 2 «create»	The <code>Operation 2</code> stereotyped by «create» represents the executed operation that creates the <i>Object</i> .
<i>Input data</i>	Input Parameters 3	They specify the information passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Object's attributes</i>	Attributes 4	They represent the characteristics of the <i>Object</i> .

Figure 21. UML representation that models the context given by CIP1

Mapping to PROV

Figure 22. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in CIP1 (Figure 21)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Class 1	prov:Entity 1 / var:postObject	The Class 1 that models the object that is created by the operation is a prov:Entity identified as var:postObject. We use the prefix <i>post</i> in this identifier because the object is the result of the executed operation.
Operation 2 «create»	prov:Activity 2 / var:operation	The execution of Operation 2 stereotyped by «create» is a prov:Activity identified by var:operation.
Input Parameters 3	prov:Entity 3 / var:input	Each parameter of Input Parameters 3 is a separate prov:Entity identified as var:input.
Attributes 4	prov:Entity 4 / var:attribute	Each attribute of Attributes 4 is a separate prov:Entity with identifier var:attribute.

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:postObject 1	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the string with the name of the class to which var:postObject 1 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:postObject is an object.
var:operation 2	prov:type / var:operationName	The value var:operationName is the name of the operation var:operation 2.
	tmpl:startTime / var:operationStartTime	The var:operationStartTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of var:operation 2.
	tmpl:endTime / var:operationEndTime	The var:operationEndTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of var:operation 2.
var:input 3	prov:value / var:inputValue	The value var:inputValue is the direct representation of var:input 3.
	u2p:typeName / var:inputType	The value var:inputType is the string with the name of the type of var:input 3.
var:attribute 4	prov:type / u2p:Attribute	The value u2p:Attribute shows that var:attribute 4 is an attribute.
	prov:value / var:attributeValue	The value var:attributeValue is the direct representation of var:attribute 4.
	u2p:attributeName / var:attributeName	The value var:attributeName is the string with the name of var:attribute 4.
	u2p:typeName / var:attributeType	The value var:attributeType is the string with the name of the type of var:attribute 4.

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:input by var:operation.
b prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:postObject by var:operation.
c prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:postObject based on var:input.
d prov:hadMember	It states that var:attribute is one of the elements in var:postObject.

Discussion

- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that *Input data* should be passed to the operation, we have considered this circumstance with the aim of covering a wider spectrum of cases. When the operation that creates the object

lacks *Input data*, the UML representation in Figure 21 will not include Input Parameters **B**. As a consequence, the resulting PROV template in Figure 22 will also lack `var:input` **B** and its associated PROV relations.

Context

The execution of an operation provokes the destruction of an object.

Key elements

- Object* The object destroyed as a consequence of the execution of the operation.
- Operation execution* The execution of the operation.

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Object</i>	Class 1	<i>Objects</i> are classified attending to their characteristics and behaviour by means of classes. Thus, we use Class 1 to represent the destroyed <i>Object</i> .
<i>Operation execution</i>	Operation 2 «destroy»	The Operation 2 stereotyped by «destroy» represents the executed operation that destroys the <i>Object</i> .

Figure 23. UML representation that models the context given by CIP2

Mapping to PROV

Figure 24. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in CIP2 (Figure 23)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Class 1	prov:Entity 1 / var:preObject	The Class 1 that models the object that is destroyed by the operation is a prov:Entity identified as var:preObject. We use the prefix <i>pre</i> in this identifier because it is the object before the execution of the operation.
Operation 2 «destroy»	prov:Activity 2 / var:operation	The execution of Operation 2 stereotyped by «destroy» is a prov:Activity identified by var:operation.

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:preObject belongs.		
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:preObject is an object.
var:operation .		
	tmpl:startTime / var:operationStartTime	The var:operationStartTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of var:operation .
	tmpl:endTime / var:operationEndTime	The var:operationEndTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of var:operation .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that var:preObject is not longer available for use.

Discussion

- This pattern is consistent with *CIP2* because the completion of the object's behaviour usually involves its destruction.

Identifier Class diagram Pattern 3 (CIP3)

Context

The execution of an operation on an object returns values of concrete object's attributes. The values are returned as they are, without any further processing. This execution does not provoke the change of the object's status.

Key elements

<i>Object</i>	The object on which the operation is executed.
<i>Operation execution</i>	The execution of the operation.
<i>Input data</i>	The information (if any) passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Output data</i>	The information obtained from the <i>Operation execution</i> .

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Object</i>	Class 1	<i>Objects</i> are classified attending to their characteristics and behaviour by means of <code>classes</code> . Thus, we use <code>Class</code> 1 to represent the <i>Object</i> on which the operation is executed.
<i>Operation execution</i>	Operation 2 «get»/«search»	The <code>Operation</code> 2 stereotyped by «get»/«search» represents the executed operation. Concretely, operations stereotyped by «get» return values of concrete <i>Object</i> 's attributes, whereas «search» is used when the operation returns elements belonging to a collection attribute of the <i>Object</i> .
<i>Input data</i>	Input Parameters 3	They specify the information passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Output data</i>	Output Parameters 4	They depict the information obtained from the <i>Operation execution</i> .

Figure 25. UML representation that models the context given by CIP3

Mapping to PROV

Figure 26. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in CIP3 (Figure 25)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Class 1	prov:Entity 1 / <code>var:preObject</code>	The Class 1 that models the object on which the operation is executed is a prov:Entity identified as <code>var:preObject</code> . We use the prefix <i>pre</i> in this identifier because it is the object before the execution of the operation.
Operation 2 «get»/«search»	prov:Activity 2 / <code>var:operation</code>	The execution of Operation 2 stereotyped by «get»/«search» is a prov:Activity identified by <code>var:operation</code> .
Input Parameters 3	prov:Entity 3 / <code>var:input</code>	Each parameter of Input Parameters 3 is a separate prov:Entity identified as <code>var:input</code> .
Output Parameters 4	prov:Entity 4.1 / <code>var:response</code> prov:Entity 4.2 / <code>var:output</code>	The information obtained by the execution of the operation is a prov:Entity identified by <code>var:response</code> . See the discussion block for an explanation about the existence of <code>var:response</code> . Each parameter of Output Parameters 4 is a separate prov:Entity identified as <code>var:output</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
<code>var:preObject</code> 1	u2p:typeName / <code>var:className</code> prov:type / u2p:Object	The value <code>var:className</code> is the string with the name of the class to which <code>var:preObject</code> 1 belongs. The value u2p:Object shows that <code>var:preObject</code> 1 is an object.
<code>var:operation</code> 2	prov:type / <code>var:operationName</code> tmpl:startTime / <code>var:operationStartTime</code> tmpl:endTime / <code>var:operationEndTime</code>	The value <code>var:operationName</code> is the name of the operation Operation 2. The <code>var:operationStartTime</code> is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of <code>var:operation</code> 2. The <code>var:operationEndTime</code> is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of <code>var:operation</code> 2.
<code>var:input</code> 3	prov:value / <code>var:inputValue</code> u2p:typeName / <code>var:inputType</code>	The value <code>var:inputValue</code> is the direct representation of <code>var:input</code> 3. The value <code>var:inputType</code> is the string with the name of the type of <code>var:input</code> 3.
<code>var:output</code> 4.2	prov:value / <code>var:outputValue</code> u2p:typeName / <code>var:outputType</code>	The value <code>var:outputValue</code> is the direct representation of <code>var:output</code> 4.2. The value <code>var:outputType</code> is the string with the name of the type of <code>var:output</code> 4.2.

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:preObject</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
b prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:input</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
c prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of <code>var:response</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
d prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of <code>var:response</code> based on <code>var:input</code> .
e prov:hadMember	It states that <code>var:output</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:response</code> .

Discussion

- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that *Input data* should be passed to the operation, we have considered this circumstance with the aim of covering a wider spectrum of cases. When the executed operation lacks *Input data*, the UML representation in Figure 25 will not include `Input Parameters` and its associated PROV relations.
- In order to homogenise the UML Class representations in *CIP1-CIP10*, *Output data* have been specified by `Output Parameters` with *return* direction. Nevertheless, these `Output Parameters` could have been modelled with either *inout* or *out* directions, having no effect in their transformation to PROV.
- A concrete nuance in this pattern is that the *Output data* (`var:output`) are not computed by the *Operation execution* (`var:operation`); that is, these data already existed before the *Operation execution*. Thus, a `prov:wasGeneratedBy` relation between `var:output` and `var:operation` does not make sense in this pattern (in contrast to *CIP4-CIP6*, and *CIP7-CIP10* when they consider *Output data*). To reflect this pattern's nuance in the PROV template and taking into account the consistency between the different kinds of patterns, we have taken inspiration from how UML sequence diagram patterns (e.g., *SeqP2*) address the *Output data*. We have made this decision because the semantics of the sequence diagrams patterns (in terms of *Output data*) bears a strong resemblance with this pattern. Thus, we have included a `prov:Entity` identified by `var:response` `prov:hadMember` (to show that such a response is composed by the concrete output values).

Context

The execution of an operation on an object returns values that are computed based on the object’s status as a whole (the values of concrete attributes involved in the computation are unknown or irrelevant). This execution does not provoke the change of the object’s status.

Key elements

- Object* The object on which the operation is executed.
- Operation execution* The execution of the operation.
- Input data* The information (if any) passed into the *Operation execution*.
- Output data* The information obtained from the *Operation execution*.

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Object</i>	Class 1	<i>Objects</i> are classified attending to their characteristics and behaviour by means of <i>classes</i> . Thus, we use <i>Class</i> 1 to represent the <i>Object</i> on which the operation is executed.
<i>Operation execution</i>	Operation 2 «process»	The <i>Operation</i> 2 stereotyped by «process» represents the executed operation. Concretely, operations stereotyped by «process» return values that are computed based on the object’s status as a whole.
<i>Input data</i>	Input Parameters 3	They specify the information passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Output data</i>	Output Parameters 4	They depict the information obtained from the <i>Operation execution</i> .

Figure 27. UML representation that models the context given by CIP4

Mapping to PROV

Figure 28. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in *CIP4* (Figure 27)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Class 1	<code>prov:Entity 1 /</code> <code>var:preObject</code>	The Class 1 that models the object on which the operation is executed is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:preObject</code> . We use the prefix <i>pre</i> in this identifier because it is the object before the execution of the operation.
Operation 2 «process»	<code>prov:Activity 2 /</code> <code>var:operation</code>	The execution of Operation 2 stereotyped by «process» is a <code>prov:Activity</code> identified by <code>var:operation</code> .
Input Parameters 3	<code>prov:Entity 3 /</code> <code>var:input</code>	Each parameter of Input Parameters 3 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:input</code> .
Output Parameters 4	<code>prov:Entity 4 /</code> <code>var:output</code>	Each parameter of Output Parameters 4 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:output</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:preObject 1	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the name of the class to which var:preObject 1 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:preObject 1 is an object.
var:operation 2	prov:type / var:operationName	The value var:operationName is the name of the operation Operation 2 .
	tmpl:startTime / var:operationStartTime	The var:operationStartTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of var:operation 2 .
	tmpl:endTime / var:operationEndTime	The var:operationEndTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of var:operation 2 .
var:input 3	prov:value / var:inputValue	The value var:inputValue is the direct representation of var:input 3 .
	u2p:typeName / var:inputType	The value var:inputType is the string with the name of the type of var:input 3 .
var:output 4	prov:value / var:outputValue	The value var:outputValue is the direct representation of var:output 4 .
	u2p:typeName / var:outputType	The value var:outputType is the string with the name of the type of var:output 4 .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:preObject by var:operation.
b prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:input by var:operation.
c prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:output by var:operation.
d prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:output based on var:input.
e prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:output based on var:preObject.

Discussion

- Among the Class Diagrams patterns, both *CIP4* and *CIP5* address the execution of an operation that returns values computed based on information included on an object. While *CIP4* considers the object's status as a whole (without taking into account the concrete attributes' values considered for its computation), *CIP5* identifies the concrete attributes used to compute such information. Thus, *CIP4* gives a coarser grained provenance than *CIP5*.
- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that *Input data* should be passed to the operation, we have considered this circumstance with the aim of covering a wider spectrum of cases. When the executed operation lacks *Input data*, the UML representation in Figure 27 will not include *Input Parameters* **3**. As a consequence, the resulting PROV template in Figure 28 will also lack var:input **3** and its associated PROV relations.
- In order to homogenise the UML Class representations in *CIP1-CIP10*, *Output data* have been specified by *Output Parameters* with *return* direction. Nevertheless, these *Output Parameters* could have been modelled with either *inout* or *out* directions, having no effect in their transformation to PROV.

Identifier Class diagram Pattern 5 (CIP5)

Context

The execution of an operation on an object returns values that are computed based on values of concrete object's attributes. This execution does not provoke the change of the object's status.

Key elements

<i>Object</i>	The object on which the operation is executed.
<i>Operation execution</i>	The execution of the operation.
<i>Input data</i>	The information (if any) passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Output data</i>	The information obtained from the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Source Object's attributes</i>	The concrete characteristics of the <i>Object</i> that are used to compute the <i>Output data</i> .

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Object</i>	Class 1	<i>Objects</i> are classified attending to their characteristics and behaviour by means of classes. Thus, we use Class 1 to represent the <i>Object</i> on which the operation is executed.
<i>Operation execution</i>	Operation 2 «predicate»/ «property»/ «void-accessor»	The Operation 2 stereotyped by «predicate»/«property»/«void-accessor» represents the executed operation. Each stereotype denotes a behaviour with specific nuances (see the discussion block); nevertheless, all of them process the <i>Output data</i> based on values of concrete object's attributes without modifying the object's status.
<i>Input data</i>	Input Parameters 3	They specify the information passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Output data</i>	Output Parameters 4	They depict the information obtained from the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Source Object's attributes</i>	Attributes 5	They represent the characteristics of the <i>Object</i> , whose values are used to compute the <i>Output data</i> .

Figure 29. UML representation that models the context given by CIP5

Mapping to PROV

Figure 30. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in *CIP5* (Figure 29)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Class 1	<code>prov:Entity</code> 1 / <code>var:preObject</code>	The Class 1 that models the object on which the operation is executed is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:preObject</code> . We use the prefix <i>pre</i> in this identifier because it is the object before the execution of the operation.
Operation 2 «predicate»/ «property»/ «void-accessor»	<code>prov:Activity</code> 2 / <code>var:operation</code>	The execution of Operation 2 stereotyped by «predicate»/ «property»/ «void-accessor» is a <code>prov:Activity</code> identified by <code>var:operation</code> .
Input Parameters 3	<code>prov:Entity</code> 3 / <code>var:input</code>	Each parameter of Input Parameters 3 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:input</code> .
Output Parameters 4	<code>prov:Entity</code> 4 / <code>var:output</code>	Each parameter of Output Parameters 4 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:output</code> .
Attributes 5	<code>prov:Entity</code> 5 / <code>var:sourceAttribute</code>	Each attribute of Attributes 5 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceAttribute</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:preObject 1	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the string with the name of the class to which var:preObject 1 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:preObject 1 is an object.
var:operation 2	prov:type / var:operationName	The value var:operationName is the name of the operation Operation 2.
	tmpl:startTime / var:operationStartTime	The var:operationStartTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of var:operation 2.
	tmpl:endTime / var:operationEndTime	The var:operationEndTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of var:operation 2.
var:input 3	prov:value / var:inputValue	The value var:inputValue is the direct representation of var:input 3.
	u2p:typeName / var:inputType	The value var:inputType is the string with the name of the type of var:input 3.
var:output 4	prov:value / var:outputValue	The value var:outputValue is the direct representation of var:output 4.
	u2p:typeName / var:outputType	The value var:outputType is the string with the name of the type of var:output 4.
var:sourceAttribute 5	prov:type / u2p:Attribute	The value u2p:Attribute shows that var:sourceAttribute 5 is an attribute.
	prov:value / var:sourceAttributeValue	The value var:sourceAttributeValue is the direct representation of var:sourceAttribute 5.
	u2p:attributeName / var:sourceAttributeName	The value var:sourceAttributeName is the string with the name of var:sourceAttribute 5.
	u2p:typeName / var:sourceAttributeType	The value var:sourceAttributeType is the string with the name of the type of var:sourceAttribute 5.

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:preObject by var:operation.
b prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:input by var:operation.
c prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:output by var:operation.
d prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:output based on var:input.
e prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:output based on var:sourceAttribute.

Discussion

- Among the Class Diagrams patterns, both CIP5 and CIP4 address the execution of an operation that returns values computed based on information included on an object. While CIP5 identifies the concrete attributes used to compute such information, CIP4 considers the object's status as a whole (without taking into account the concrete attributes' values considered for its computation). Thus, CIP5 gives a finer grained provenance than CIP4.
- A question that might arise is why in Figure 30 var:sourceAttribute 5 is not associated with var:preObject 1 (which represents the object with the status before the execution of the operation) by means of a prov:hadMember relation, whether var:sourceAttribute 5 is an attribute of var:preObject 1. We have made this decision because an object that acts as a var:preObject in an operation execution, was a var:postObject (which represents the object with the

status after the execution of the operation) in a previous operation execution. Thus, the attributes associated to such an object in a `var:preObject` were registered when it previously played the role of `var:postObject`.

- The stereotypes `«predicate»`, `«property»`, and `«void-accessor»` denote behaviours with specific nuances. Nevertheless, these nuances do not have impact in the translation into PROV since all of them compute *Output data* based on concrete object's attributes without modifying the object's status. Concretely, `«predicate»` denotes that the operation returns boolean values, `«property»` does not restrict the type of the returned values, and `«void-accessor»` returns the information through a parameter. As we said previously, there is no distinction in the transformation into PROV; however, some of the nuances given by the stereotypes will be included in the generated provenance through the values assigned to the template's variables. For instance, `«predicate»` defines the *Output data* as boolean, fact that is included in the provenance through the value assigned to `var:outputType` in `var:output` .
- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that *Input data* should be passed to the operation, we have considered this circumstance with the aim of covering a wider spectrum of cases. When the executed operation lacks *Input data*, the UML representation in Figure 29 will not include *Input Parameters* and its associated PROV relations.

Context

The execution of an operation on an object changes the object’s status as a whole (the concrete modified attributes are unknown or irrelevant).

Key elements

<i>Object</i>	The object on which the operation is executed.
<i>Pre-operation object</i>	The object with the status before the execution of the operation.
<i>Post-operation object</i>	The object with the status after the execution of the operation.
<i>Operation execution</i>	The execution of the operation.
<i>Input data</i>	The information (if any) passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Object’s attributes</i>	All the characteristics of the <i>Object</i> .

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Object</i>	Class 1	<i>Objects</i> are classified attending to their characteristics and behaviour by means of <i>classes</i> . Thus, we use <i>Class</i> 1 to represent the <i>Object</i> both before and after the execution of the operation (<i>Pre-operation object</i> and <i>Post-operation object</i> , respectively).
<i>Operation execution</i>	Operation 2 «command»/ «non-void-command»	The <i>Operation</i> 2 stereotyped by «command»/«non-void-command» represents the executed operation. These stereotypes denote that the object changes its status, without considering the concrete modified attributes. They differ in that an operation stereotyped by «non-void-command» returns information, while a «command» stereotyped operation does not. <i>Note:</i> the PROV template depicted in Figure 32 corresponds to an operation stereotyped by «command» (see the discussion block for an explanation of the transformation of the operations stereotyped by «non-void-command»).
<i>Input data</i>	Input Parameters 5	They specify the information passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Object’s attributes</i>	Attributes 4	They represent the characteristics of the <i>Object</i> .

Figure 31. UML representation that models the context given by CIP6

Mapping to PROV

Figure 32. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in CIP6 (Figure 31)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Class 1	<code>prov:Entity</code> 1.1 / <code>var:preObject</code>	The <i>Pre-operation object</i> , i.e. the object with the status before the execution of the operation, which is represented by Class 1, is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:preObject</code> .
	<code>prov:Entity</code> 1.2 / <code>var:postObject</code>	The <i>Post-operation object</i> , i.e. the object with the status after the execution of the operation, which is represented by Class 1, is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:postObject</code> .
Operation 2 «command»/ «non-void-command»	<code>prov:Activity</code> 2 / <code>var:operation</code>	The execution of Operation 2 stereotyped by «command»/«non-void-command» is a <code>prov:Activity</code> identified by <code>var:operation</code> .
Input Parameters 3	<code>prov:Entity</code> 3 / <code>var:input</code>	Each parameter of Input Parameters 3 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:input</code> .
Attributes 4	<code>prov:Entity</code> 4 / <code>var:attribute</code>	Each attribute of Attributes 4 is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:attribute</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:preObject 1.1	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the name of the class to which var:preObject 1.1 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:preObject 1.1 is an object.
var:postObject 1.2	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the name of the class to which var:postObject 1.2 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:postObject 1.2 is an object.
var:operation 2	prov:type / var:operationName	The value var:operationName is the name of the operation var:operation 2 .
	tmpl:startTime / var:operationStartTime	The var:operationStartTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of var:operation 2 .
	tmpl:endTime / var:operationEndTime	The var:operationEndTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of var:operation 2 .
var:input 3	prov:value / var:inputValue	The value var:inputValue is the direct representation of var:input 3 .
	u2p:typeName / var:inputType	The value var:inputType is the string with the name of the type of var:input 3 .
var:attribute 4	prov:type / u2p:Attribute	The value u2p:Attribute shows that var:attribute 4 is an attribute.
	prov:value / var:attributeValue	The value var:attributeValue is the direct representation of attribute 4 .
	u2p:attributeName / var:attributeName	The value var:attributeName is the string with the name of attribute 4 .
	u2p:typeName / var:attributeType	The value var:attributeType is the string with the name of the type of var:attribute 4 .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:input by var:operation.
b prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:preObject by var:operation.
c prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:postObject by var:operation.
d prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of var:preObject resulting in var:postObject.
e prov:hadMember	It states that var:attribute is one of the elements in var:postObject.
f prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:postObject based on var:input.

Discussion

- Among the Class Diagrams patterns, patterns from [CIP6](#) to [CIP10](#) address the execution of operations that change an object's status. While, [CIP6](#) changes the object's status as a whole (being the concrete modified attributes unknown or irrelevant), in patterns [CIP7-CIP10](#) the concrete attributes modified by the *Operation execution* are explicitly known. In contrast to [CIP7](#) which directly sets the information passed into the *Operation execution* as values of concrete object's attributes, the other mentioned patterns use such information to change the object's status as a whole or the values of concrete object's attributes. It must also be noted that patterns [CIP9](#) and [CIP10](#) address the execution of operations which remove or add elements from/into an object's collection attribute, while patterns [CIP7](#) and [CIP8](#) affect either a univalued attribute or a collection attribute as a whole.
- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that *Input data* should be passed to the operation, we do not consider this circumstance with the aim of covering a wider spectrum of cases. When the executed operation lacks *Input*

data, the UML representation in Figure 31 will not include `Input Parameters` 3. As a consequence, the resulting PROV template in Figure 32 will also lack `var:input` 3 and its associated PROV relations.

- A question that might arise is why in Figure 32 `var:attribute` 4 is associated with `var:postObject` 1.2 (which represents the object with the status after the execution of the operation), but it is not associated with `var:preObject` 1.1 (the object with the status before the execution). We have made this decision because an object that acts as a `var:preObject` in an operation execution, was a `var:postObject` in a previous operation execution. Thus, the attributes associated to such an object in a `var:preObject` were registered when it previously played the role of `var:postObject`.
- Stereotypes `«command»` and `«non-void-command»` denote that the operation performs a change to the object's status as a whole. They differ in that an operation stereotyped by `«non-void-command»` returns information, while a `«command»` stereotyped operation does not. Due to the fact that the context of this pattern does not explicitly state that output data are obtained from the *Operation execution*, we represented this context in UML using the stereotype `«command»` (see Figure 31).

Aiming at giving an insight into how the inclusion of *Output data* affects both the UML representation and the resulting PROV template, Figure 33 depicts a UML representation with (1) the stereotype `«non-void-command»` and (2) *Output data* modelled as `Output Parameters` 5 (in this case with *return* direction, though the translation of *inout* and *out* directions would be equivalent). Figure 34 depicts its transformation into PROV. Both Figure 33 and 34 highlight the elements related to the inclusion of the *Output data* by blurring the elements coming from Figure 31 and 32, respectively.

Figure 33. UML representation that models the context given by *CIP6*, including `Output Parameters`.

Figure 34. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in *CIP6*, including `Output Parameters` (Figure 33)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
<code>Output Parameters</code> 5	<code>prov:Entity</code> 5 / <code>var:output</code>	Each parameter of <code>Output Parameters</code> 5 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:output</code> .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of <code>var:output</code> based on <code>var:input</code> .
prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of <code>var:output</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of <code>var:output</code> based on <code>var:preObject</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
<code>var:output</code> .		
	u2p:typeName / <code>var:outputType</code>	The value <code>var:outputType</code> is the string with the name of the type of <code>var:output</code> .

Identifier Class diagram Pattern 7 (CIP7)

Context

The execution of an operation on an object directly sets the information passed to the operation as values of concrete object's attributes, thus provoking a change in the object's status.

Key elements

<i>Object</i>	The object on which the operation is executed.
<i>Pre-operation object</i>	The object with the status before the execution of the operation.
<i>Post-operation object</i>	The object with the status after the execution of the operation.
<i>Operation execution</i>	The execution of the operation.
<i>Input data</i>	The information passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Object's attributes</i>	All the characteristics of the <i>Object</i> . Since, as a consequence of the <i>Operation execution</i> , the values of some attributes change, we have identified: <i>Modified attributes</i> The modified <i>Object's attributes</i> . <i>Unmodified attributes</i> The not modified <i>Object's attributes</i> .

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Object</i>	Class 1	<i>Objects</i> are classified attending to their characteristics and behaviour by means of <code>classes</code> . Thus, we use <code>Class 1</code> to represent the <i>Object</i> both before and after the execution of the operation (<i>Pre-operation object</i> and <i>Post-operation object</i> , respectively).
<i>Operation execution</i>	Operation 2 «set»	The <code>Operation 2</code> stereotyped by «set» represents the executed operation. Concretely, the stereotype «set» denotes that <i>Input data</i> are directly set as values of concrete attributes of the object.
<i>Input data</i>	Input Parameters 3	They specify the information passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Object's attributes</i>	Attributes 4	They represent the characteristics of the <i>Object</i> .

Figure 35. UML representation that models the context given by CIP7

Mapping to PROV

Figure 36. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in CIP7 (Figure 35)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Class 1	<code>prov:Entity</code> 1.1 / <code>var:preObject</code>	The <i>Pre-operation object</i> , i.e. the object with the status before the execution of the operation, which is represented by Class 1, is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:preObject</code> .
	<code>prov:Entity</code> 1.2 / <code>var:postObject</code>	The <i>Post-operation object</i> , i.e. the object with the status after the execution of the operation, which is represented by Class 1, is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:postObject</code> .
Operation 2 «set»	<code>prov:Activity</code> 2 / <code>var:operation</code>	The execution of Operation 2 stereotyped by «set» is a <code>prov:Activity</code> identified by <code>var:operation</code> .
Input Parameters 3	<code>prov:Entity</code> 3 / <code>var:input</code>	Each parameter of Input Parameters 3 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:input</code> .
Attributes 4	None /	The <i>Modified attributes</i> (belonging to Attributes 4) are already mapped to <code>var:input</code> . For further information, see the discussion.
	<code>prov:Entity</code> 4.2 / <code>var:attribute</code>	Each <i>Unmodified attribute</i> (belonging to Attributes 4) is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with identifier <code>var:attribute</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:preObject 1.1	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the string with the name of the class to which var:preObject 1.1 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:preObject 1.1 is an object.
var:postObject 1.2	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the string with the name of the class to which var:postObject 1.2 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:postObject 1.2 is an object.
var:operation 2	prov:type / var:operationName	The value var:operationName is the name of the operation var:operation 2 .
	tmpl:startTime / var:operationStartTime	The var:operationStartTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of var:operation 2 .
	tmpl:endTime / var:operationEndTime	The var:operationEndTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of var:operation 2 .
var:input 3	prov:value / var:inputValue	The value var:inputValue is the direct representation of var:input 3 .
	u2p:typeName / var:inputType	The value var:inputType is the string with the name of the type of var:input 3 .
	prov:type / u2p:Attribute	The value u2p:Attribute shows that var:input 3 is an attribute.
	u2p:attributeName / var:attributeName	The value var:attributeName is the string with the name of the attribute var:input 3 .
var:attribute 4.2	prov:type / u2p:Attribute	The value u2p:Attribute shows that var:attribute 4.2 is an attribute.
	prov:value / var:attributeValue	The value var:attributeValue is the direct representation of var:attribute 4.2 .
	u2p:attributeName / var:attributeName	The value var:attributeName is the string with the name of var:attribute 4.2 .
	u2p:typeName / var:attributeType	The value var:attributeType is the string with the name of the type of var:attribute 4.2 .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:input by var:operation.
b prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:preObject by var:operation.
c prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:postObject by var:operation.
d prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of var:preObject resulting in var:postObject.
e prov:hadMember	It states that var:attribute is one of the elements in var:postObject.
f prov:hadMember	It states that var:input is one of the elements in var:postObject. This is due to the fact that in this context the input information is directly set as values of certain attributes of the Object.

Discussion

- Among the Class Diagrams patterns, patterns from [CIP6](#) to [CIP10](#) address the execution of operations that change an object's status. While, [CIP6](#) changes the object's status as a whole (being the concrete modified attributes unknown or irrelevant), in patterns [CIP7-CIP10](#) the concrete attributes modified by the *Operation execution* are explicitly known. In contrast to [CIP7](#) which directly sets the information passed into the *Operation execution* as values of concrete object's attributes, the

other mentioned patterns use such information to change the object's status as a whole or the values of concrete object's attributes. It must also be noted that patterns *CIP9* and *CIP10* address the execution of operations which remove or add elements from/into an object's collection attribute, while patterns *CIP7* and *CIP8* affect either a univalued attribute or a collection attribute as a whole.

- A question that might arise is why in Figure 36 `var:attribute 4.2` is associated with `var:postObject 1.2` (which represents the object with the status after the execution of the operation), but it is not associated with `var:preObject 1.1` (the object with the status before the execution). We have made this decision because an object that acts as a `var:preObject` in an operation execution, was a `var:postObject` in a previous operation execution. Thus, the attributes associated to such an object in a `var:preObject` were registered when it previously played the role of `var:postObject`.
- This context states that the *Input data* are directly set as values of certain object's attributes, which means that the *Input data* correspond directly to the *Modified attributes*. This fact is represented in the PROV template by means of the pair attribute/value `prov:type/u2p:Attribute` of `var:input 3`, and the relation `prov:hadMember` between `var:postObject 1.2` and `var:input 3`. Additionally, `var:input 3` has the attribute `u2p:attributeName` whose value `var:attributeName` denotes the name of the modified attribute.
- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that output data should be obtained from the *Operation execution*, this could be the case. However, we do not include this output data in this pattern description to avoid overburden both the UML and PROV explanations with information out of the scope of the *context*.

Aiming at giving an insight into how the inclusion of *Output data* affects both the UML representation and the resulting PROV template, Figure 37 depicts a UML representation with the *Output data* modelled as *Output Parameters* `5` (in this case with *return* direction, though the translation of *inout* and *out* directions would be equivalent). Figure 38 depicts its transformation into PROV. Both Figure 37 and 38 highlight the elements related to the inclusion of the *Output data* by blurring the elements coming from Figure 35 and 36, respectively.

Figure 37. UML representation that models the context given by *CIP7*, including *Output Parameters*.

Figure 38. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in *CIP7*, including *Output Parameters* (Figure 37)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Output Parameters is a separate prov:Entity identified as var:output.		

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:output based on var:input.
prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:output by var:operation.
prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:output based on var:preObject.

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:output .		
	u2p:typeName / var:outputType	The value var:outputType is the string with the name of the type of var:output .

Identifier *Class diagram Pattern 8 (CIP8)*

Context

The execution of an operation on an object changes the values of concrete object’s attributes, thus provoking a change in the object’s status.

Key elements

- Object* The object on which the operation is executed.
 - Pre-operation object* The object with the status before the execution of the operation.
 - Post-operation object* The object with the status after the execution of the operation.
- Operation execution* The execution of the operation.
- Input data* The information (if any) passed into the *Operation execution*.
- Object’s attributes* All the characteristics of the *Object*. Since, as a consequence of the *Operation execution*, the values of some attributes change, we have identified:
 - Modified attributes* The modified *Object’s attributes*.
 - Unmodified attributes* The not modified *Object’s attributes*.

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Object</i>	Class 1	<i>Objects</i> are classified attending to their characteristics and behaviour by means of <i>classes</i> . Thus, we use <i>Class 1</i> to represent the <i>Object</i> both before and after the execution of the operation (<i>Pre-operation object</i> and <i>Post-operation object</i> , respectively).
<i>Operation execution</i>	Operation 2 «modify»	The <i>Operation 2</i> stereotyped by «modify» represents the executed operation. Concretely, the stereotype «modify» denotes that concrete attributes of the object are modified.
<i>Input data</i>	Input Parameters 3	They specify the information passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Object’s attributes</i>	Attributes 4	They represent the characteristics of the <i>Object</i> .

Figure 39. UML representation that models the context given by *CIP8*

Mapping to PROV

Figure 40. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in *CIP8* (Figure 39)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Class 1	<code>prov:Entity</code> 1.1 / <code>var:preObject</code>	The <i>Pre-operation object</i> , i.e. the object with the status before the execution of the operation, which is represented by Class 1, is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:preObject</code> .
	<code>prov:Entity</code> 1.2 / <code>var:postObject</code>	The <i>Post-operation object</i> , i.e. the object with the status after the execution of the operation, which is represented by Class 1, is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:postObject</code> .
Operation 2 «modify»	<code>prov:Activity</code> 2 / <code>var:operation</code>	The execution of Operation 2 stereotyped by «modify» is a <code>prov:Activity</code> identified by <code>var:operation</code> .
Input Parameters 3	<code>prov:Entity</code> 3 / <code>var:input</code>	Each parameter of Input Parameters 3 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:input</code> .
Attributes 4	<code>prov:Entity</code> 4.1 / <code>var:modifiedAttribute</code>	Each <i>Modified attribute</i> (belonging to Attributes 4) is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with identifier <code>var:modifiedAttribute</code> .
	<code>prov:Entity</code> 4.2 / <code>var:attribute</code>	Each <i>Unmodified attribute</i> (belonging to Attributes 4) is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with identifier <code>var:attribute</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:preObject 1.1	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the string with the name of the class to which var:preObject 1.1 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:preObject 1.1 is an object.
var:postObject 1.2	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the string with the name of the class to which var:postObject 1.2 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:postObject 1.2 is an object.
var:operation 2	prov:type / var:operationName	The value var:operationName is the name of the operation var:operation 2 .
	tmpl:startTime / var:operationStartTime	The var:operationStartTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of var:operation 2 .
	tmpl:endTime / var:operationEndTime	The var:operationEndTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of var:operation 2 .
var:input 3	prov:value / var:inputValue	The value var:inputValue is the direct representation of var:input 3 .
	u2p:typeName / var:inputType	The value var:inputType is the string with the name of the type of var:input 3 .
var:modifiedAttribute 4.1	prov:type / u2p:Attribute	The value u2p:Attribute shows that var:modifiedAttribute 4.1 is an attribute.
	prov:value / var:modifiedAttrValue	The value var:attributeValue is the direct representation of var:modifiedAttribute 4.1 .
	u2p:attributeName / var:modifiedAttrName	The value var:modifiedAttrName is the string with the name of var:modifiedAttribute 4.1 .
	u2p:typeName / var:modifiedAttrType	The value var:attributeType is the string with the name of the type of var:modifiedAttribute 4.1 .
var:attribute 4.2	prov:type / u2p:Attribute	The value u2p:Attribute shows that var:attribute 4.2 is an attribute.
	prov:value / var:attributeValue	The value var:attributeValue is the direct representation of var:attribute 4.2 .
	u2p:attributeName / var:attributeName	The value var:attributeName is the string with the name of var:attribute 4.2 .
	u2p:typeName / var:attributeType	The value var:attributeType is the string with the name of the type of var:attribute 4.2 .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:input by var:operation.
b prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:preObject by var:operation.
c prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:postObject by var:operation.
d prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of var:preObject resulting in var:postObject.
e prov:hadMember	It states that var:attribute is one of the elements in var:postObject.
f prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:postObject based on var:input.
g prov:hadMember	It states that var:modifiedAttribute is one of the elements in var:postObject.
h prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:modifiedAttribute based on var:input.
i prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:modifiedAttribute by var:operation.

Discussion

- Among the Class Diagrams patterns, patterns from *CIP6* to *CIP10* address the execution of operations that change an object's status. While, *CIP6* changes the object's status as a whole (being the concrete modified attributes unknown or irrelevant), in patterns *CIP7-CIP10* the concrete attributes modified by the *Operation execution* are explicitly known. In contrast to *CIP7* which directly sets the information passed into the *Operation execution* as values of concrete object's attributes, the other mentioned patterns use such information to change the object's status as a whole or the values of concrete object's attributes. It must also be noted that patterns *CIP9* and *CIP10* address the execution of operations which remove or add elements from/into an object's collection attribute, while patterns *CIP7* and *CIP8* affect either a univalued attribute or a collection attribute as a whole.
- A question that might arise is why in Figure 40 `var:attribute` (the object with the status before the execution). We have made this decision because an object that acts as a `var:preObject` in an operation execution, was a `var:postObject` in a previous operation execution. Thus, the attributes associated to such an object in a `var:preObject` were registered when it previously played the role of `var:postObject`.
- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that *Input data* should be passed to the operation, we do not to consider this circumstance with the aim of covering a wider spectrum of cases. When the executed operation lacks *Input data*, the UML representation in Figure 39 will not include `Input Parameters` and its associated PROV relations.
- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that output data should be obtained from the *Operation execution*, this could be the case. However, we do not include this output data in this pattern description to avoid overburden both the UML and PROV explanations with information out of the scope of the *context*.

Aiming at giving an insight into how the inclusion of *Output data* affects both UML representation and the resulting PROV template, Figure 41 depicts a UML representation with the *Output data* modelled as `Output Parameters` (in this case with *return* direction, though the translation of *inout* and *out* directions would be equivalent). Figure 42 depicts its transformation into PROV. Both Figure 41 and 42 highlight the elements related to the inclusion of the *Output data* by blurring the elements coming from Figure 39 and 40, respectively.

Figure 41. UML representation that models the context given by *CIP8*, including `Output Parameters`.

Figure 42. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in CIP8, including Output Parameters (Figure 41)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Output Parameters →	<code>prov:Entity</code> → / <code>var:output</code>	Each parameter of Output Parameters → is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:output</code> .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
i <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the construction of <code>var:output</code> based on <code>var:input</code> .
k <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:output</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
l <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the construction of <code>var:output</code> based on <code>var:preObject</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
<code>var:output</code> →	<code>prov:value</code> / <code>var:outputValue</code>	The value <code>var:outputValue</code> is the direct representation of <code>var:output</code> →.
	<code>u2p:typeName</code> / <code>var:outputType</code>	The value <code>var:outputType</code> is the string with the name of the type of <code>var:output</code> →.

Identifier Class diagram Pattern 9 (CIP9)

Context

The execution of an operation on an object removes element(s) from a concrete object’s collection attribute, thus provoking a change in the object’s status.

Key elements

<i>Object</i>	The object on which the operation is executed. <i>Pre-operation object</i> The object with the status before the execution of the operation. <i>Post-operation object</i> The object with the status after the execution of the operation.
<i>Operation execution</i>	The execution of the operation.
<i>Input data</i>	The information (if any) passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Object’s attributes</i>	All the characteristics of the <i>Object</i> . Since, as a consequence of the <i>Operation execution</i> , a concrete collection attribute changes, we have identified: <i>Modified collection attribute</i> The modified <i>Object’s attribute</i> . <i>Unmodified attributes</i> The not modified <i>Object’s attributes</i> .

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Object</i>	Class 1	<i>Objects</i> are classified attending to their characteristics and behaviour by means of classes . Thus, we use Class 1 to represent the <i>Object</i> both before and after the execution of the operation (<i>Pre-operation object</i> and <i>Post-operation object</i> , respectively).
<i>Operation execution</i>	Operation 2 «remove»	The Operation 2 stereotyped by «remove» represents the executed operation. Concretely, the stereotype «remove» denotes that an element (or elements) of a concrete collection attribute is removed.
<i>Input data</i>	Input Parameters 3	They specify the information passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Object’s attributes</i>	Attributes 4	They represent the characteristics of the <i>Object</i> .

Figure 43. UML representation that models the context given by CIP9

Mapping to PROV

Figure 44. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in *CIP9* (Figure 43)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Class 1	<code>prov:Entity</code> 1.1 / <code>var:preObject</code>	The <i>Pre-operation object</i> , i.e. the object with the status before the execution of the operation, which is represented by Class 1, is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:preObject</code> .
	<code>prov:Entity</code> 1.2 / <code>var:postObject</code>	The <i>Post-operation object</i> , i.e. the object with the status after the execution of the operation, which is represented by Class 1, is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:postObject</code> .
Operation 2 «remove»	<code>prov:Activity</code> 2 / <code>var:operation</code>	The execution of Operation 2 stereotyped by «remove» is a <code>prov:Activity</code> identified by <code>var:operation</code> .
Input Parameters 3	<code>prov:Entity</code> 3 / <code>var:input</code>	Each parameter of Input Parameters 3 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:input</code> .
Attributes 4	<code>prov:Entity</code> 4.1 / <code>var:modCollAttribute</code>	The <i>Modified collection attribute</i> (belonging to Attributes 4) is a <code>prov:Entity</code> with identifier <code>var:modCollAttribute</code> . Additionally, each element in this collection is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:collElement</code> 4.1.1
	<code>prov:Entity</code> 4.2 / <code>var:attribute</code>	Each <i>Unmodified attribute</i> (belonging to Attributes 4) is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with identifier <code>var:attribute</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:preObject 1.1	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the string with the name of the class to which var:preObject 1.1 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:preObject 1.1 is an object.
var:postObject 1.2	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the string with the name of the class to which var:postObject 1.2 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:postObject 1.2 is an object.
var:operation 2	prov:type / var:operationName	The value var:operationName is the name of the operation var:operation 2 .
	tmpl:startTime / var:operationStartTime	The var:operationStartTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of var:operation 2 .
	tmpl:endTime / var:operationEndTime	The var:operationEndTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of var:operation 2 .
var:input 3	prov:value / var:inputValue	The value var:inputValue is the direct representation of var:input 3 .
	u2p:typeName / var:inputType	The value var:inputType is the string with the name of the type of var:input 3 .
var:modCollAttribute 4.1	prov:type / u2p:Attribute	The value u2p:Attribute shows that var:modCollAttribute 4.1 is an attribute.
	prov:value / var:modCollAttributeValue	The value var:modCollAttributeValue is the direct representation of var:modCollAttribute 4.1 .
	u2p:attributeName / var:modCollAttributeName	The value var:modCollAttributeName is the string with the name of var:modCollAttribute 4.1 .
	u2p:typeName / var:modCollAttributeType	The value var:modCollAttributeType is the string with the name of the type of var:modCollAttribute 4.1 .
var:attribute 4.2	prov:type / u2p:Attribute	The value u2p:Attribute shows that var:attribute 4.2 is an attribute.
	prov:value / var:attributeValue	The value var:attributeValue is the direct representation of var:attribute 4.2 .
	u2p:attributeName / var:attributeName	The value var:attributeName is the string with the name of var:attribute 4.2 .
	u2p:typeName / var:attributeType	The value var:attributeType is the string with the name of the type of var:attribute 4.2 .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a <code>prov:used</code>	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:input</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
b <code>prov:used</code>	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:preObject</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
c <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:postObject</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
d <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:preObject</code> resulting in <code>var:postObject</code> .
e <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:attribute</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:postObject</code> .
f <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the construction of <code>var:postObject</code> based on <code>var:input</code> .
g <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:modCollAttribute</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:postObject</code> .
h <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the construction of <code>var:modCollAttribute</code> based on <code>var:input</code> .
i <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:modCollAttribute</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
j <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:collElement</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:modCollAttribute</code> .

Discussion

- Among the Class Diagrams patterns, patterns from *CIP6* to *CIP10* address the execution of operations that change an object's status. While, *CIP6* changes the object's status as a whole (being the concrete modified attributes unknown or irrelevant), in patterns *CIP7-CIP10* the concrete attributes modified by the *Operation execution* are explicitly known. In contrast to *CIP7* which directly sets the information passed into the *Operation execution* as values of concrete object's attributes, the other mentioned patterns use such information to change the object's status as a whole or the values of concrete object's attributes. It must also be noted that patterns *CIP9* and *CIP10* address the execution of operations which remove or add elements from/into an object's collection attribute, while patterns *CIP7* and *CIP8* affect either a univalued attribute or a collection attribute as a whole.
- A question that might arise is why in Figure 44 `var:attribute` is associated with `var:postObject` (which represents the object with the status after the execution of the operation), but it is not associated with `var:preObject` (the object with the status before the execution). We have made this decision because an object that acts as a `var:preObject` in an operation execution, was a `var:postObject` in a previous operation execution. Thus, the attributes associated to such an object in a `var:preObject` were registered when it previously played the role of `var:postObject`.
- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that *Input data* should be passed to the operation, we have considered this circumstance with the aim of covering a wider spectrum of cases. When the executed operation lacks *Input data*, the UML representation in Figure 43 will not include *Input Parameters*. As a consequence, the resulting PROV template in Figure 44 will also lack `var:input` and its associated PROV relations.
- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that output data should be obtained from the *Operation execution*, this could be the case. However, we have decided not to include this output data in this pattern description to avoid overburden both the UML and PROV explanations with information out of the scope of the *context*.

Aiming at giving an insight into how the inclusion of *Output data* affects both UML representation and the resulting PROV template, Figure 45 depicts a UML representation with the *Output data* modelled as *Output Parameters* (in this case with *return* direction, though the translation of *inout* and *out* directions would be equivalent). Figure 46 depicts its transformation into PROV. Both Figure 45 and 46 highlight the elements related to the inclusion of the *Output data* by blurring the elements coming from Figure 43 and 44, respectively.

Figure 45. UML representation that models the context given by CIP9, including Output Parameters.

Figure 46. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in CIP9, including Output Parameters (Figure 45)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Output Parameters 5	prov:Entity 5 / var:output	Each parameter of Output Parameters 5 is a separate prov:Entity identified as var:output.

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
k prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:output based on var:input.
l prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:output by var:operation.
m prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the construction of var:output based on var:preObject.

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:output 5	prov:value / var:outputValue	The value var:outputValue is the direct representation of var:output 5.
	u2p:typeName / var:outputType	The value var:outputType is the string with the name of the type of var:output 5.

Identifier Class diagram Pattern 10 (CIP10)

Context

The execution of an operation on an object directly adds the information passed to the operation as new element(s) of a concrete object's collection attribute, thus provoking a change in the object's status.

Key elements

<i>Object</i>	The object to which the operation to be executed belongs.
<i>Pre-operation object</i>	The object with the status before the execution of the operation.
<i>Post-operation object</i>	The object with the status after the execution of the operation.
<i>Operation execution</i>	The execution of the behaviour specified by the operation.
<i>Input data</i>	The information passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Object's attributes</i>	All the characteristics of the <i>Object</i> . Since, as a consequence of the <i>Operation execution</i> , a concrete collection attribute changes, we have identified: <i>Modified collection attribute</i> The modified <i>Object's attribute</i> . <i>Unmodified attributes</i> The not modified <i>Object's attributes</i> .

UML Diagram

Key Element	UML	Rationale
<i>Object</i>	Class 1	<i>Objects</i> are classified attending to their characteristics and behaviour by means of <code>classes</code> . Thus, we use <code>Class 1</code> to represent the <i>Object</i> both before and after the execution of the operation (<i>Pre-operation object</i> and <i>Post-operation object</i> , respectively).
<i>Operation execution</i>	Operation 2 «add»	The <code>Operation 2</code> stereotyped by «add» represents the executed operation. Concretely, the stereotype «add» denotes that a new element (or elements) is directly added to a concrete collection attribute.
<i>Input data</i>	Input Parameters 3	They specify the information passed into the <i>Operation execution</i> .
<i>Object's attributes</i>	Attributes 4	They represent the characteristics of the <i>Object</i> .

Figure 47. UML representation that models the context given by CIP10

Mapping to PROV

Figure 48. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in CIP10 (Figure 47)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Class 1	<code>prov:Entity 1.1</code> / <code>var:preObject</code>	The <i>Pre-operation object</i> , i.e. the object with the status before the execution of the operation, which is represented by Class 1, is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:preObject</code> .
	<code>prov:Entity 1.2</code> / <code>var:postObject</code>	The <i>Post-operation object</i> , i.e. the object with the status after the execution of the operation, which is represented by Class 1, is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:postObject</code> .
Operation 2 «add»	<code>prov:Activity 2</code> / <code>var:operation</code>	The execution of Operation 2 stereotyped by «add» is a <code>prov:Activity</code> identified by <code>var:operation</code> .
Input Parameters 3	<code>prov:Entity 3</code> / <code>var:input</code>	Each parameter of Input Parameters 3 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:input</code> .
Attributes 4	<code>prov:Entity 4.1</code> / <code>var:modCollAttribute</code>	The <i>Modified collection attribute</i> (belonging to Attributes 4) is a <code>prov:Entity</code> with identifier <code>var:modCollAttribute</code> . Additionally, each element in this collection is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:collElement 4.1.1</code>
	<code>prov:Entity 4.2</code> / <code>var:attribute</code>	Each <i>Unmodified attribute</i> (belonging to Attributes 4) is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with identifier <code>var:attribute</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
var:preObject 1.1	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the string with the name of the class to which var:preObject 1.1 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:preObject 1.1 is an object.
var:postObject 1.2	u2p:typeName / var:className	The value var:className is the string with the name of the class to which var:postObject 1.2 belongs.
	prov:type / u2p:Object	The value u2p:Object shows that var:postObject 1.2 is an object.
var:operation 2	prov:type / var:operationName	The value var:operationName is the name of the operation var:operation 2 .
	tmpl:startTime / var:operationStartTime	The var:operationStartTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the start of var:operation 2 .
	tmpl:endTime / var:operationEndTime	The var:operationEndTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the end of var:operation 2 .
var:input 3	prov:value / var:inputValue	The value var:inputValue is the direct representation of var:input 3 .
	u2p:typeName / var:inputType	The value var:inputType is the string with the name of the type of var:input 3 .
var:modCollAttribute 4.1	prov:type / u2p:Attribute	The value u2p:Attribute shows that var:modCollAttribute 4.1 is an attribute.
	prov:value / var:modCollAttributeValue	The value var:modCollAttributeValue is the direct representation of var:modCollAttribute 4.1 .
	u2p:attributeName / var:modCollAttributeName	The value var:modCollAttributeName is the string with the name of var:modCollAttribute 4.1 .
	u2p:typeName / var:modCollAttributeType	The value var:modCollAttributeType is the string with the name of the type of var:modCollAttribute 4.1 .
var:attribute 4.2	prov:type / u2p:Attribute	The value u2p:Attribute shows that attribute 4.2 is an attribute.
	prov:value / var:attributeValue	The value var:attributeValue is the direct representation of attribute 4.2 .
	u2p:attributeName / var:attributeName	The value var:attributeName is the string with the name of attribute 4.2 .
	u2p:typeName / var:attributeType	The value var:attributeType is the string with the name of the type of attribute 4.2 .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a <code>prov:used</code>	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:input</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
b <code>prov:used</code>	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:preObject</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
c <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:postObject</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
d <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:preObject</code> resulting in <code>var:postObject</code> .
e <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:attribute</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:postObject</code> .
f <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the construction of <code>var:postObject</code> based on <code>var:input</code> .
g <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:modCollAttribute</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:postObject</code> .
h <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:input</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:modCollAttribute</code> . This is due to the fact that in this context the input information is directly added to the object's collection attribute.
i <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:modCollAttribute</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
j <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:collElement</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:modCollAttribute</code> .

Discussion

- Among the Class Diagrams patterns, patterns from *CIP6* to *CIP10* address the execution of operations that change an object's status. While, *CIP6* changes the object's status as a whole (being the concrete modified attributes unknown or irrelevant), in patterns *CIP7-CIP10* the concrete attributes modified by the *Operation execution* are explicitly known. In contrast to *CIP7* which directly sets the information passed into the *Operation execution* as values of concrete object's attributes, the other mentioned patterns use such information to change the object's status as a whole or the values of concrete object's attributes. It must also be noted that patterns *CIP9* and *CIP10* address the execution of operations which remove or add elements from/into an object's collection attribute, while patterns *CIP7* and *CIP8* affect either a univalued attribute or a collection attribute as a whole.
- A question that might arise is why in Figure 48 `var:attribute` **4** is associated with `var:postObject` **1.2** (which represents the object with the status after the execution of the operation), but it is not associated with `var:preObject` **1.1** (the object with the status before the execution). We have made this decision because an object that acts as a `var:preObject` in an operation execution, was a `var:postObject` in a previous operation execution. Thus, the attributes associated to such an object in a `var:preObject` were registered when it previously played the role of `var:postObject`.
- Although the *context* of this pattern does not explicitly state that output data should be obtained from the *Operation execution*, this could be the case. However, we do not include this output data in this pattern description to avoid overburden both the UML and PROV explanations with information out of the scope of the *context*.

Aiming at giving an insight into how the inclusion of *Output data* affects both UML representation and the resulting PROV template, Figure 49 depicts a UML representation with the *Output data* modelled as *Output Parameters* **5** (in this case with *return* direction, though the translation of *inout* and *out* directions would be equivalent). Figure 50 depicts its transformation into PROV. Both Figure 49 and 50 highlight the elements related to the inclusion of the *Output data* by blurring the elements coming from Figure 47 and 48, respectively.

Figure 49. UML representation that models the context given by *CIP10*, including *Output Parameters*.

Figure 50. PROV template generated from the UML representation used in *CIP10*, including Output Parameters (Figure 49)

PROV elements

UML	PROV / id	Rationale
Output Parameters 5	<code>prov:Entity</code> 5 / <code>var:output</code>	Each parameter of Output Parameters 5 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> identified as <code>var:output</code> .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
k <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the construction of <code>var:output</code> based on <code>var:input</code> .
i <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:output</code> by <code>var:operation</code> .
m <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the construction of <code>var:output</code> based on <code>var:preObject</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute / Value	Description
<code>var:output</code> 5	<code>prov:value</code> / <code>var:outputValue</code>	The value <code>var:outputValue</code> is the direct representation of <code>var:output</code> 5 .
	<code>u2p:typeName</code> / <code>var:outputType</code>	The value <code>var:outputType</code> is the string with the name of the type of <code>var:output</code> 5 .

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Appendix A Taxonomy of Class' operations

Depending on their nature, operations implicitly have specific semantics that can also provide information of interest for provenance capture. In order to provide UML Class diagrams with such additional semantics to be included in the generated PROV templates, we have stated a taxonomy of operations given by a set of stereotypes to be included in such diagrams. The taxonomy is based on that given by Dragan et al. [7], which has been enriched with additional stereotypes aimed at identifying extra/further operation's semantics not considered in [7] (marked with an asterisk in Table 2).

Table 2. Extension of the taxonomy given in [7] showing the categories of UML Class's operations considered in our proposal. Stereotypes with an asterisk denote those included by our proposal.

Category	Stereotype name	Description
Creational	create	The operation creates an object.
	destroy	The operation destroys an object.
Structural Accessor	get	The operation returns values of concrete attributes of an object.
	search*	The operation returns elements belonging to a concrete collection attribute of an object.
	process*	The operation returns values that are computed based the object's status as a whole (the specific attributes used for the calculation are not relevant).
	predicate	The operation returns boolean values that are computed based on concrete attributes of an object.
	property	The operation returns values (of any type) that are computed based on concrete attributes of an object.
	void-accessor	The operation returns values (of any type) that are computed based on concrete attributes of an object. These values are returned by means of parameters.
Structural Mutator	command	The operation changes the status of an object as a whole (the modified attributes are unknown or irrelevant). It does not return information.
	non-void-command	The operation changes the status of an object as a whole (the modified attributes are unknown or irrelevant). It does return information.
	set	The operation directly sets the information passed to the operation as values of concrete attributes of an object.
	modify*	The operation modifies concrete attributes of an object.
	remove*	The operation removes an element from a concrete collection attribute of an object.
	add*	The operation adds an element on a concrete collection attribute of an object.

INTEGRATING PROVENANCE CAPTURE AND UML WITH UML2PROV: PRINCIPLES AND EXPERIENCE

IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

Carlos Sáenz-Adán^{1*}, Beatriz Pérez¹, Francisco J. García-Izquierdo¹, Luc Moreau²

¹*Dept. of Mathematics and Computer Science, Univ. of La Rioja, La Rioja, Spain,
{carlos.saenz,beatriz.perez,francisco.garcia}@unirioja.es*

²*Dept. of Informatics, King's College London, London, UK,
luc.moreau@kcl.ac.uk*

This appendix provides a detailed description of the Model Driven Development (MDD) approach we have followed for implementing UML2PROV, which we succinctly explained in the paper [1]. This approach is presented schematically in Figure 1, below. MDD focuses on models, rather than on computer programs, so that the code programs are automatically generated from them by using a refinement process [2]. This process could entail one or various transformations that describe the way in which a source model is translated into another final target. Depending on the type of source and target elements of the transformation, we can distinguish between *model to model transformations* (M2M), in which both are models, and *model to text transformations*, which define transformations from a model to a final text.

Our solution for implementing UML2PROV following an MDD approach comprises both M2M and M2T transformations. Among the different existing tools to implement M2M and M2T transformations, we have used the Atlas Transformation Language (ATL) [3] and Xtend [4]. On the one hand, in case of M2M transformations, we have used

Figure 1: Our MDD-based implementation proposal.

ATL [3] for being one of the most widely used M2M transformation languages, in addition to provide an IDE developed on top of Eclipse. On the other hand, M2T transformations have been implemented by means of Xtend [4] for several reasons, among which we note that it integrates seamlessly with the Eclipse Java IDE, and that it has a large user community and a significant number of available examples.

Next, in Section 1, we explain the MDD transformations we have defined to implement our UML to PROV templates transformation patterns. Later, in Section 2, we first give details regarding our strategy to implement the BGM (*Bindings Generation Module*) for an application and, second, we provide our MDD-based proposal to automatically generate it.

1 Automatization of the UML to PROV Templates transformation patterns

Generally speaking, our proposal for implementing our transformation patterns takes as source the *UML diagram models* of the application and automatically generates the *PROV template files* (Figure 1). Instead of performing a one-step direct transformation between such source and target elements, we have decided to define an intermediate step by means of which *UML diagram models* are first translated into a transitional model (*template models*) which will be finally translated into the *PROV template files* in PROV-N. This strategy allows us to draw a distinction between the translation from *UML diagram models* into *template models*, and the way in which the *template models* are serialised, in this case PROV-N. As a result, our proposal follows an MDD-based tool chain that comprises two transformations (see Figure 2): first, an M2M transformation identified by T1, whose implementation is explained in Subsection 1.1, and second, an M2T transformation identified by T2, which is explained in Subsection 1.2.

Figure 2: Detailed MDD-based implementation of the PROV templates generation process

1.1 Transformation T1: from UML diagram models to template models

This M2M transformation takes as source the *UML diagram models*, conforming to the UML metamodel [5], and generates the corresponding *template models*, conforming to the PROV metamodel [6]. To that end, our transformation patterns [7] serve as the basis for the definition of an ATL module made up of a set of ATL rules. Each rule addresses one transformation pattern describing how the UML elements identified by the pattern are mapped to the specific PROV elements, and their relations, constituting a *template model*.

As an example of such ATL rules, Table 1 shows how an excerpt of the ATL rule defined to implement the *CIP1* pattern looks like. Such a pattern deals with operations that construct an object. This table depicts, per each fragment of the

Table 1: An excerpt of the ATL rule implementing *CIP1*. For each fragment in the excerpt (“ATL source code” column), the PROV elements it generates are provided (“Template model” column) together with a description of the transformation (“Description” column) as well as the graphical notation of the template model (last column).

ATL source code	Template model	Description	Graphical representation of the template model
rule Operation2Document{ from operation: UMLOperation(operation.hasStereotype('create')) [...]		It states that the rule is applied to all the UML operations to which CIP1 refers. That is, those operations with the stereotype «create»	
to postObjectEn: PROV!Entity (id <- 'var:postObject', ...),	<entity id="var:postObject"/>	It creates an <entity> with identifier var:postObject.	
operationAct: PROV!Activity (id <- 'var:operation', ...),	<activity id="var:operation"/>	This excerpt is in charge of generating an <activity> identified by var:operation.	
wgb: PROV!Generation (entity <- postObjectEnID, activity <- operationActID),	<wasGeneratedBy> <entity ref="var:postObject"/> <activity ref="var:operation"/> </activity>	This excerpt is responsible for linking var:postObject with var:operation by means of the PROV relation <wasGeneratedBy>.	
do{ if(existIn){ thisModule.newEnt('var:input', doc); thisModule.genDer('var:postObject', 'var:input', doc); thisModule.genU('var:input', ' var:operation', doc); }	<entity id="var:input"/> <wasDerivedFrom> <generatedEntity ref="var:postObject"/> <usedEntity ref="var:input"/> </wasDerivedFrom> <used> <activity ref="var:operation"/> <entity ref="var:input"/> </used>	In case there are UML Input Parameters, it creates an <entity> identified by var:input*, and its relations <wasDerivedFrom> and <used> with var:postObject and var:operation, respectively.	
if(hasAttr){ thisModule.newEnt('var:attribute', doc); thisModule.genMe('var:attribute', 'var:postObject', doc); } [...]	<entity id="var:attribute"/> <hadMember> <collection ref="var:postObject"/> <entity ref="var:attribute"/> </hadMember>	If there are UML Attributes in the class to which the operation belongs, it generates an <entity> identified by var:attribute*, and the PROV relation <hadMember> between var:postObject and var:attribute.	

*Although CIP1 states that each attribute/input parameter is a separate prov:Entity identified as var:attribute/var:input, we have decided to merge all the entities with the same identifier. Nevertheless, this decision does not have any effect on the bindings, since each var:input and var:attribute will be given several values (one for each input parameter and attribute, respectively).

rule (see first column), the PROV elements/relations in the template that are generated by such a fragment (see column “Template model”). We can see how PROV elements such as document, entity and activity, as well as PROV relations such as used and wasGeneratedBy, appear in the column as <document>, <entity>, <activity>, <used>, and <wasGeneratedBy>. Additionally, the description of the transformation together with the graphical notation of the template model being generated are given in the two right-hand columns.

1.2 Transformation T2: from template models to PROV template files

T2 corresponds to an M2T transformation that takes as source the *template models* resulting from T1, and generates the *PROV template files* in PROV-N format. This transformation is implemented in an Xtend class (see Figure 3) which contains *template expressions* that associate each PROV element/relation with its associated PROV-N representation. Among the defined Xtend template expressions (declared by the explicit keyword def), there is a main template (line 2) which is in charge of translating each PROV <document> appearing in the *template models* into a *PROV template*, defined as a .provn extension text file. This PROV-N document will include not only fixed text (shown in green in Figure 3), but also the text resulting from instantiating those Xtend templates in charge of translating the PROV elements/relations included in the <document> (lines from 3 to 15). As a way of example, Figure 3 also depicts the Xtend template (line 16) which translates each <entity> into the corresponding prov:Entity in PROV-N.

```

1: class PROVNGenerator {
2:   def manageDocument(Document doc, PrintStream o) {
      o.println('
      document
      prefix prov <http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#>
      prefix tpl <http://openprovenance.org/tmpl#>
      prefix var <http://openprovenance.org/var#>
      prefix exe <http://example.org/>
      prefix u2p <http://uml2prov.org/>
      bundle exe:bundle1
      ')
3:   for (entity : doc.entity)    {o.println(manageEntity(entity))}
4:   for (agent : doc.agent)      {o.println(manageAgent(agent))}
5:   for (activity : doc.activity) {o.println(manageActivity(activity))}
6:   for (wsb : doc.wasStartedBy) {o.println(wStartedByTemplate(wsb))}
7:   for (wgb : doc.wasGeneratedBy) {o.println(wgbTemplate(wgb))}
8:   for (u : doc.used)           {o.println(usedTemplate(u))}
9:   for (wInfB : doc.wasInformedBy) {o.println(wInfByTemplate(wInfB))}
10:  for (wInvB : doc.wasInvalidatedBy) {o.println(wibTemplate(wInvB))}
11:  for (wdf : doc.wasDerivedFrom)  {o.println(wdfTemplate(wdf))}
12:  for (hm : doc.hadMember)        {o.println(hmTemplate(hm))} //
13:  for (so : doc.specializationOf) {o.println(spOTemplate(so))} //
14:  for (wat : doc.wasAttributedTo) {o.println(watTemplate(wat))}
15:  for (waw : doc.wasAssociatedWith) {o.println(wawTemplate(waw))}
      o.println('
      endBundle
      endDocument');
    }
16: def manageEntity(Entity entity) {
      ""entity(«entity.id», «entityAttributeTemplate(entity)»)""
    }
    ...
  }
}

```

Figure 3: Xtend class including the template defined for each `<document>` and `<entity>` in the *template models*.

2 BGM generation automation

Here, we explain in detail a reference implementation for the automatic generation of the BGM corresponding to a certain application, starting from its UML design. Below, we will explain our strategy for implementing the BGM for a concrete application starting from its UML design (Subsection 2.1), and later we move on to describe the process we have defined to automatically generate a BGM (Subsection 2.2).

2.1 Towards an implementation of the BGM

Aimed at providing an implementation of a BGM, there are several issues a developer may consider to manage the provenance data for creating bindings. The first one is referred to when and how the bindings are generated and stored. For example, applications may store the provenance data using usual logs, delaying the construction of bindings

until after runtime. Alternatively, applications could directly construct the bindings at runtime. The second aspect refers to when provenance documents are generated and which storage system is used. For example, the bindings could be accumulated locally in memory, delaying the generation of the provenance documents (i.e., the expansion of templates), and thus their storage (e.g., database, files, . . .) until after runtime. Alternatively, the strategy could be to expand the templates with the accumulated bindings on runtime, storing the provenance documents as the application is executed.

Taking into account these issues, we have defined a generic *event*-driven proposal to implement the BGMs. *Events* are notable occurrences that happen while the application is running, whereas *listeners* contain the behaviour for processing the *events*. Concretely, our proposal for capturing the provenance data is driven by the execution of operations, for this reason, we have identified four notable types of occurrences that take place during the execution of an operation, and which correspond to four types of *events*, respectively. Two of these *events* are related to the start and end of an operation, whereas the two remaining *event* types refer to the collection of values associated with the two types of variables stated in [9] (*group variables* and *statement-level variable*). On the one hand, a *group variable* is a type of variable that occurs in a mandatory identifier position. On the other hand, a *statement-level variable* is a variable that occurs in an attribute-value pair (either in attribute position or in value position), or that occurs in optional identifier position. So as to give an insight into them, Figure 4 shows a `prov:Activity` in PROV-N with variables occurring in different positions.

In this context, the *event* types we have identified are the following:

- (1) *operationStart* and (2) *operationEnd*. These types of *events* refer to the start and end of an operation execution, respectively. They are of interest when developers want to create and store sets of bindings associated with a concrete operation execution, instead of storing each binding independently.
- (3) *newBinding*. This type of *event* refers to the occurrence of the collection of a provenance value associated with a *group variable*. For instance, the collection of a value associated with the variable `var:operation` in Figure 4 will trigger an *event* of type *newBinding* since `var:operation` occurs in an identifier position.
- (4) *newValueBinding*. This type of *event* refers to the occurrence of the collection of a provenance value associated with a *statement-level variable*. For instance, the collection of values linked with `var:operationStartTime` and `var:operationName` in Figure 4 fires *newValueBinding events* due to `var:operationStartTime` occurring in an optional position, and `var:operationName` occurring in a value position.

Our reference implementation of BGM is made up of four main components written in Java (see Figure 5) which are divided into two main groups. The first group, which is referred to as *context independent components*, is made up

Figure 4: PROV activity in PROV-N [8] with different types of variables. Additionally, it is shown a table associating each variable with its type.

Figure 5: UML CD depicting our reference implementation for the BGM.

of those elements that do not depend on the source *UML diagram models*, and therefore, they are the same in all the BGMs. This group is made up of the *BGMEventListener*, *BGMEvent*, and *BGMEventManager* (see components in white background in Figure 5). The second group, called *context dependent components*, consists of those elements whose implementation depends on the source *UML diagram models*. In our reference implementation the only element included in this group is the *BGMEventInstrumenter* (depicted in grey background in Figure 5).

- *BGMEventListener*. It is an interface that defines four operations for managing each type of *event* (*operationStart*, *operationEnd*, *newBinding*, and *newValueBinding*). These operations have an input parameter of type *BGMEvent* (see below) that contains the provenance data to be processed. The implementation of these operations constitutes the mechanism used by a class implementing the *listener* interface to generate, manage, and store the bindings. As commented before, the developer just needs to choose the mechanisms that best suits her/his requirements by developing classes implementing the *BGMEventListener* interface. Later, in Section 2.1.1, we will give a reference implementation of this interface. At this point, we remark that with the aim of simplifying the design, we group all the operations for managing the abovementioned *event* types in the same interface (*BGMEventListener*). In case a developer is not interested in handling a concrete *event*, she/he can leave empty the implementation of its corresponding operation.
- *BGMEvent*. This component is used to carry information about the occurrence of an *event*. We have decided to use the same class *BGMEvent* to contain information about the four event types (*operationStart*, *operationEnd*, *newBinding*, *newValueBinding*) because this information can be stored using the same structure. Concretely, this structure will contain the provenance data necessary for constructing the bindings. Among them, we remark the attribute

Figure 6: Structure overview of a reference implementation of the *BGMEventInstrumenter* in AspectJ

`varName` for the name of the variable, and the attribute value for the value associated with such a variable. See Figure 5. For instance, in case of an *operationStart* event, a *BGMEvent* object could have an attribute `varName` containing the value "var:operationStartTime", and an attribute value with the value "2018-12-20T12:54:20". Another example could be a *BGMEvent* object with information about a *newBinding* event. It could contain an attribute `varName` with the value "var:operation", and the attribute value containing "exe:nameOfOperation-300691".

- *BGMEventManager*. In some cases, to have only one *listener* for generating, managing, and storing bindings could be not enough, and the same happens with the mechanisms for generating and storing provenance. For instance, one provenance consumer may be interested in replicating the information by storing both the provenance data, and the bindings generated from them in different storage systems. Aiming at addressing these scenarios, we have included the *BGMEventManager* with two responsibilities: to manage a list of subscribed *listeners*, and to disseminate the objects of type *BGMEvent* among them.
- *BGMEventInstrumenter*. As we stated in the paper [1], to manually adapt the source code of an application would be a valid option to capture provenance data. However, this option would require to traverse the whole code of the concrete application identifying the classes that will be the source of the events, and additionally, those places inside these classes where *events* will be fired. Then, the manual adaptation of the source code would need to include in those places instructions for constructing *BGMEvent* objects with the provenance data, and disseminating them among the *listeners*. This task constitutes a tedious, time-consuming and error-prone process. What is worse, the manual adaptation could incur in such provenance capture code instructions scattered across all the application classes, making their maintenance a cumbersome task.

In contrast, we propose to use the Aspect Oriented Programming (AOP) [10] paradigm for implementing what we have named *BGMEventInstrumenter*. AOP aims at improving the modularity of software systems, by capturing inherently scattered functionality, often called *cross-cutting concerns*, (e.g., the capture of provenance), and placing that functionality apart from the actual application's source code. Our reference implementation is developed in AspectJ, an AOP extension created for Java [11], and it consists of an *aspect* which is made up of an *advice* with *pointcuts* (see Figure 6). On the one hand, the *pointcuts* identify locations within the application code where a concern may be included. In our case, we identify operation calls and constructor invocations from which we want to fire *events* (i.e., to collect provenance). On the other hand, the *advice* is the behaviour executed when the *pointcuts* are matched. In AspectJ, *advices* can be executed at three different places: *before*, *around*, and *after* the *pointcuts*. Due to the fact that our identified *events* can occur both before and after operations calls and constructors

invocations, we have used an *around advice* for executing custom behaviours before and after the actual behaviour. These custom behaviours consist of constructing objects of type *BGMEvent* and disseminating them to the *listeners* (by invoking the `disseminateEvent` operation from *BGMEventManager*). In the end, as a pre-compilation step, the AspectJ *weaver* automatically integrates the behaviour from the *aspects* into the locations specified by the *pointcuts* at compilation time. In this way, our AOP approach does not require a manual intervention for adapting the source code, and automatically collects provenance data in a transparent way for software developers, which directly incurs in fulfilling the requirements *R1-R3* stated in the paper [1].

2.1.1 Example of a class implementing the *BGMEventListener*

Taking into account the structure depicted in Figure 5, we provide the users with a concrete implementation of the interface *BGMEventListener* (class that we name *ConcreteBGMEventListener*). This class implements the four operations defined in the *BGMEventListener* so that the bindings are generated and accumulated in memory, and when the execution of each tracked operation finishes, they are shipped to the MongoDB database. Thus, this implementation is only in charge of generating and storing bindings, delaying the expansion of templates. In this way, the users can decide not only which templates to expand, but also when to expand them.

2.2 Automatization of the implementation of the BGM

The BGM for an application is automatically generated by means of an M2T transformation referred to as T3 in Figure 7. Such a transformation has been implemented by means of an Xtend class that takes as source the application's *UML diagram models*, conforming the UML metamodel [5], and generates the java code of the BGM.

Figure 7: Detailed MDD-based implementation of the BGM for an application.

As we stated previously, the source code of the *context independent components* (i.e., *BGMEvent*, *BGMEventManager*, and *BGMEventListener*) is the same for all the BGMs; thus, it does not depend on the *UML diagram models* used as input in the transformation. Conversely, the implementation of the *context dependent component* (i.e., *BGMEventInstrumenter*) depends on the source *UML diagram models*.

Our strategy for automatically generating the BGM is to implement an Xtend class that (1) directly creates all the *context independent components*, and (2) generates the *BGMEventInstrumenter* based on the source UML design. Whilst we could have provided users with a separate library including all the *context independent components*, we have made the decision of generating them automatically together with the *BGMEventInstrumenter* in order to reduce the code dependencies.

In particular, the Xtend class generates the *BGMEventInstrumenter* so that its *pointcuts* identify the calls to operations and invocations of constructors. Concretely, these *pointcuts* correspond to (1) the invocations of the constructors of classes involved in the UML design, and (2) calls of operations that are involved in the source: SqDs (i.e., the operations whose calls are modelled by means of UML Messages), SMDs (i.e., the operations whose occurrences are associated with UML Events), and CDs, (i.e., the operations that are modelled by UML Operations). The remainder source code of the *BGMEventInstrumenter* (that is, the *advise*) is also shared by all the BGMs.

2.3 Fulfilment of BGM requirements

The reference implementation of the BGMs given in this document fulfils the five requirement stated in the paper [1] (identified from *R1* to *R5*). As we previously stated, requirements from *R1* to *R3* have been met thanks to the AOP implementation of the *BGMEventInstrumenter* explained in Section 2.1. Regarding the requirements *R4* and *R5*, we note that they have been satisfied because of the suitable ad hoc implementation of the *BGMEventInstrumenter* for a concrete application (explained in Section 2.2). On the one hand, the automatically generated *pointcuts* inside the *BGMEventInstrumenter* ensures that the collected bindings are associated with at least one PROV template (requirement *R4*). This is because the *pointcuts* correspond to operations calls and constructors invocations that are modelled in the UML design, and therefore they have an associated PROV template. On the other hand, the requirement *R5* is fulfilled since the transformation T3 has been implemented so that it respects the names of the variables appearing in the PROV templates generated by the chain of transformations T1-T2.

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INTEGRATING PROVENANCE CAPTURE AND UML WITH UML2PROV: PRINCIPLES AND EXPERIENCE

TAXONOMY OF CLASS' OPERATIONS

Carlos Sáenz-Adán^{1*}, Beatriz Pérez¹, Francisco J. García-Izquierdo¹, Luc Moreau²

¹*Dept. of Mathematics and Computer Science, Univ. of La Rioja, La Rioja, Spain,
{carlos.saenz,beatriz.perez,francisco.garcia}@unirioja.es*

²*Dept. of Informatics, King's College London, London, UK,
luc.moreau@kcl.ac.uk*

1 Introduction

Depending on their nature, operations have specific semantics which can also produce information of interest for provenance capture. For instance, the key factors involved in the execution of an operation such as *getName* (accessing an object's attribute) are different from the ones related to *setName* (modifying an object's attribute), and consequently, the provenance information captured from the execution of both operations must be different. Taking this into account, we are interested in identifying a taxonomy of operations which covers the vast varied range of operation's types of interest for provenance capture. Based on this taxonomy, we can define our CDs to PROV template patterns so that the generated templates can provide concrete provenance information depending on the operation's semantics.

2 A taxonomy of operations

To define our taxonomy, we undertook a literature search looking for different categorizations of operations based on their behaviours. We distinguished the approaches that present a more general classification of operations such as [3], from those that provide a more fine grained taxonomy of operations such as [1] or, more remarkably, the work presented by Dragan et al. in [2], which is one of the most complete. Dragan et al.'s taxonomy is based both on how an operation accesses data (i.e., an operation changes the object's status or leaves it unchanged), and on its behavioural characteristics (i.e., creational, structural...). Such a taxonomy is expressed as a classification of operations' *Stereotypes*. These UML *Stereotypes* are extension mechanisms that allow us to complement each CD's *operation* with specific semantic information regarding its category within the taxonomy, thus linking the *operation* with its corresponding semantics. The notation for a *Stereotype* is a string with the stereotype name between a pair of guillemets (e.g., «add»).

This taxonomy define five categories: (1) *Creational* refers to operations responsible for creating or destroying objects of the class. (2) *Structural Accessor* refers to operations that return information regarding the attributes of the object to which it belongs, without changing the state of the object. (3) *Structural Mutator* corresponds to operations that change the state of the object to which it belongs. (4) *Collaborational* which helps define the communication between objects and how objects are controlled in the system. Finally, (5) *Degenerate* corresponds to operations which give us little information about.

Our proposal (see Table 1), which is inspired from the Dragan et al.'s one [2], includes additional stereotypes (marked with an asterisk) not initially considered in the original taxonomy: the *search*, *add* and *remove* stereotypes, which cover operations for the management of collection attributes (such as search, addition or removal, respectively); the *process* stereotype, for operations returning information based on the whole object's internal structure; and *modify*, for operations that modify a specific attribute without setting an input value directly. We have not considered the categories *collaborational* and *degenerate* since they represent behaviours already modelled by SqDs (such as the communication between objects, given by *collaborational*), or reflect aspects that cannot be tackled without checking the source code (e.g., *degenerate* category). Below, we explain the behaviour represented by each stereotype.

Table 1: Extension of the taxonomy given in [2] showing the categories of UML Class' operations considered in our proposal. Stereotypes with an asterisk denote those included by our proposal.

Category	Stereotype name	Description
Creational	create	The operation creates an object.
	destroy	The operation destroys an object.
Structural <i>Accessor</i>	get	The operation returns values of concrete attributes of an object.
	search*	The operation returns elements belonging to a concrete collection attribute of an object.
	process*	The operation returns values that are computed based the object's status as a whole.
	predicate	The operation returns boolean values that are computed based on concrete attributes of an object.
	property	The operation returns values (of any type) that are computed based on concrete attributes of an object.
	void-accessor	The operation, by means of a parameter, returns values (of any type) that are computed based on concrete attributes of an object.
Structural <i>Mutator</i>	command	The operation changes the status of an object as a whole (the modified attributes are unknown or irrelevant). It does not return information.
	non-void-command	The operation changes the status of an object as a whole (the modified attributes are unknown or irrelevant). It does return information.
	set	The operation directly sets the information passed to the operation as values of concrete attributes of an object.
	modify*	The operation modifies concrete attributes of an object.
	remove*	The operation removes an element from a concrete collection attribute of an object.
	add*	The operation adds an element on a concrete collection attribute of an object.

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INTEGRATING PROVENANCE CAPTURE AND UML WITH UML2PROV: PRINCIPLES AND EXPERIENCE

SEQUENCE OF INTERACTIONS WITH GELJ

Carlos Sáenz-Adán^{1*}, Beatriz Pérez¹, Francisco J. García-Izquierdo¹, Luc Moreau²

¹*Dept. of Mathematics and Computer Science, Univ. of La Rioja, La Rioja, Spain,
{carlos.saenz,beatriz.perez,francisco.garcia}@unirioja.es*

²*Dept. of Informatics, King's College London, London, UK,
luc.moreau@kcl.ac.uk*

In this document, we show the sequence of interactions (see Figure 1) among the 13 substeps of the experiment wizard of GelJ, which has been selected to conduct the evaluation of UML2PROV as unbiased as possible. Each rounded rectangle in Figure 1 corresponds to a task performed by the user. Each task is named using the label provided by the GelJ interface (e.g., *crop* for cropping the image). Empty rounded rectangles mean that no tasks are performed in that step. Additionally, rounded rectangles with associated text may include a label at the right top, denoting the number of times that such a task has been performed. Finally, we use green arrows to specify that the user has proceeded to the *next* step, or red arrows to show that the user goes *back* to the previous step.

Figure 1: Sequence of interactions used to perform the evaluation.

INTEGRATING PROVENANCE CAPTURE AND UML WITH UML2PROV: PRINCIPLES AND EXPERIENCE

CASE STUDY: UNIVERSITY EXAMPLE

Carlos Sáenz-Adán^{1*}, Beatriz Pérez¹, Francisco J. García-Izquierdo¹, Luc Moreau²

¹*Dept. of Mathematics and Computer Science, Univ. of La Rioja, La Rioja, Spain,
{carlos.saenz,beatriz.perez,francisco.garcia}@unirioja.es*

²*Dept. of Informatics, King's College London, London, UK,
luc.moreau@kcl.ac.uk*

The results presented in this appendix are part of the evaluation we have made to show the feasibility of our proposal UML2PROV presented in the paper [1]. In that paper, we show the evaluation we have made of our proposal by applying it both to a legacy application named GelJ [2] built without UML (*retroactive* scenario) and to an academic application built from a UML design (*proactive* scenario). While in [2] we mainly focus on the GelJ case study because it is more complex, here we describe in detail the application of UML2PROV to the *proactive* scenario, the University example, using the same evaluation aspects we have taken into account in the paper [1]. We would like to note that, in contrast to the GelJ case study, in the academic University example we play the role of software designers, developers, provenance consumers and potential users.

The University case study correspond to an example, slightly modified from [3], related to the enrolment and attendance of students to seminars that are held during a University course. This application mainly allows users to perform three actions in the context of a university. The first allows administrative staff to check if a student can apply for a given seminar. The second offers the possibility of enrolling a student in a seminar. Finally, the third is related to the overall process which encompasses the evaluation of students' performance in such seminars through exams, considering from the time an exam is prepared until the student is informed of her/his mark. It is worth noting that the University application's database only contains information about specific characteristics of the elements conforming the system (e.g., students, seminars, exams, and so on). It does not keep information about the requests for checking if it is possible to apply for a seminar, or for example, the specific process of preparing and taking an exam, and informing about the mark.

In order to give an unbiased evaluation of our approach, based on a representative use of the University system, we have defined an example execution considering several scenarios (see Algorithm 1). Concretely, this execution is divided in two phases: in the first phase (lines from 2 to 9), 25 students ask for enrolling into a seminar (line 4), after the affirmative response, they are enrolled into the seminar (line 6), and finally, the student' performance evaluation begins

by proceeding with an exam (line 7). In the second phase (lines 10-13), another 25 students (already enrolled) proceed with an exam (line 12). Consequently, the defined benchmark involves the execution of the three cited functionalities of the application. The performance of this example execution incurs in the execution of about 1700 operations in the tool's source code.

```

1 seminar ← findSeminar(idSeminar);
2 for i ← 0 to 24 do
3   student ← findStudent(i);
4   allowEnrol ← askStaffForEnrolling(student, seminar);
5   if allowEnrol then
6     enrolStudent(student, seminar);
7     proceedWithExam(student, seminar);
8   end
9 end
10 for i ← 25 to 49 do
11   student ← findStudent(i);
12   proceedWithExam(student, seminar);
13 end

```

Algorithm 1: Example execution algorithm in pseudocode

The evaluation was run in the same personal computer and under the same conditions as in the GelJ case study.

1 Particularities of the application modes in this case study

In Table 1 we show the tasks comprising each application mode for this case study. This information can be used to compare the characteristics of each mode.

Table 1: Overview of tasks in UML2PROV *Application Modes*.

Task	Case study - University		
	App. Mode 1	App. Mode 2	App. Mode 3
T1. Identify the complete CD	–	–	–
T2. Identify provenance requirements	‡	–	–
T3. Identify classes/operations involved in provenance requirements	‡	–	–
T4. Discard not identified classes/operations	‡	–	–
T5. Add stereotypes to selected operations	‡	–	–
T6. Identify SqDs	‡	–	–
T7. Design SMDs of selected classes	–	–	–

‡ Performed automatically | † Requires manual effort | †/‡ Requires semi-manual effort | – Non executed task

Application Mode 1

Regarding task T2, since in this case study there are no final users interested in the generated provenance, it is not possible to obtain the provenance requirements from them. For this reason, as described previously, we have simulated that we are the final users that raised the provenance questions that serve as requirements. To conduct an unbiased

evaluation, we have not defined the questions from scratch, but we have drawn inspiration from the questions appearing in the First Provenance Challenge [4], adapting them to obtain questions regarding the performance of exams. The resulting questions, depicted in Table 2, represent the provenance requirements (called *provenance use case questions* in PrIme).

Table 2: Questions identified from Q1 to Q5 about the University case study, together with University classes involved in answering those questions.

ID	Question	Identified Classes
Q1	What is the set of activities that has led an exam as it is?	Exam Teacher Student
Q2	How many answers have an exam?	Exam
Q3	When is the student informed about the mark of an exam?	Exam
Q4	Who has signed the exam?	Exam Student
Q5	What is the date of an exam?	Exam

In this case study, all the UML CD, SqD and SMD diagrams are available at the beginning of the evaluation. Thus, all the performed tasks are tailoring tasks. Neither to reverse engineer the CD (T1) nor to design the SMDs (T7) are required. Similarly, it is not necessary to reverse engineer SqD. We just have to select the SqDs related to the provenance requirements (T6).

Inspired by the second phase of PrIme, from the UML design we have identified those classes and operations (called *actors* in PrIme) involved in answering the identified questions (T3), following the same procedure described for GelJ. The result was the identification of 3 classes and 11 operations out of 11 classes and 37 operations that compose University application (i.e., $\sim 27\%$ of the classes and $\sim 29\%$ of the operations of the University application were used. The rest of classes/operations were discarded (T4). These classes are shown in column “Identified Classes” of Table 2. In addition, to obtain more meaningful provenance, we assigned stereotypes to the UML operations in class diagram (T5). As for SqDs, we selected those related to the provenance requirements. This task resulted in a set of 25 messages. Regarding SMDs, we used the UML SMDs for those classes whose states are related to the provenance requirements. This led to 2 SMDs with 7 states, and 9 transitions.

As in the GelJ case study, the greatest effort goes into identifying the provenance requirements (T2) and selecting the classes and operations involved (T3 and T4).

Application Modes 2 and 3

In these modes no tasks are performed, so no effort has been made. More specifically, we have taken the original SqDs and CDs without tailoring them (CDs, in both modes and SqDs, in Mode 2). Concretely, the UML design encompasses a CD with 11 classes and 37 operations, and a set of SqDs with 25 messages in total.

1.1 Analysis

Next, we analyse those evaluation aspects explicitly related to the University case study.

Table 3: Variables evaluated for the considered UML2PROV *Application Modes* in the University case study.

Application Mode (UML diagrams)	No. templates	Total size of templates	No. Variables	No. Set of bindings	Sets of bindings size (MB)	Expanded templates size (MB)	No. executions instrumented operations	% instrumented executed operations	Execution time (ms)	Time overhead
Mode 1 (SqD, SMD, CD)	25	20KB	115	687	1,4	2,3	687	41,79%	656,19	25,92%
Mode 2 (SqD, CD)	63	47KB	269	1.644	2,0	3,3	1.644	100%	802,29	53,96%
Mode 3 (CD)	40	26KB	137	1.644	1,9	2,0	1.644	100%	747,31	43,41%

1.1.1 Aspect 1: Generation of the provenance design

In line with the results obtained for GelJ, the time-cost for generating the templates, a few milliseconds per template, is considered negligible compared to the time-cost of performing this task manually (this information is not depicted in Table 3 because we consider it trivial). As for the implications of the followed mode, the results show that the closer the UML design fits the application provenance requirements, the less templates are generated and consequently, the smaller their total size and the faster their generation. Table 3 shows that Mode 1 (with a tailored UML design), results in the lowest number of templates (25). However, Modes 2 and 3 present a higher number of templates (63 and 40, respectively). These figures confirm that a greater initial effort to more accurately tailor the UML according to a set of provenance requirements, results in fewer templates.

1.1.2 Aspect 2: Instrumentation of the application

The column “No. variables” of Table 3 depicts the number of instructions included in the BGM for bindings generation. Mode 1, with least UML elements, leads to the BGM with fewest instructions (115) against Modes 2 and 3 that generate BGMs with more instructions within (269 and 137, respectively). Given these results, we can see that although Mode 1 has fewer number of instructions, the difference with Mode 3 is relatively small (115 vs 137 instructions). This small difference is because of three main reasons. First, due to the small difference between the considered operations in Mode 1 (11 operations, see Table 1), and Mode 3 (37 operations). Second, because Mode 1 generates templates from SqDs and SMDs, unlikely Mode 3. Third, since Mode 1 considers CDs with stereotypes, which incurs in templates with more variables.

Nevertheless, these results are in the line of those obtained from GelJ [1]: the effort devoted to more precisely tailor the UML design according to the provenance requirements results in a simplification of the BGM, which has significant implications in the performance.

1.1.3 Aspect 4: Storage and Run-time overhead

The overhead attributable to provenance capture is associated with the number of executions of instrumented operations (see Table 3, where column “No. set of bindings” matches this number). In this case study, Mode 1 generates the least number of set of bindings (687), and consequently, led to the least run-time overhead (25.92%) and storage needs (1.4MB). Conversely, Modes 2 and 3 generated more set of bindings (1,644 both of them), and yielded the more time overhead (53.96% and 43.41%, respectively) and storage needs (2MB and 1.9MB). Mode 2 will always require more storage since it takes into account the whole Class diagram (unlike Mode 1) and additionally, it does not discard the Sequence diagrams (in contrast to Mode 3).

Table 4: For each mode, it is indicated if questions Q1-Q5 of Table 2 can be answered completely (C), sufficiently (S), partially (P) or cannot be answered (N). If a question can be answered, the number of elements of the provenance involved in its answer appears in brackets.

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5
Mode 1	S(5)	S(6)	S(3)	S(3)	S(2)
Mode 2	C(12)	S(6)	N	S(3)	S(2)
Mode 3	C(12)	S(6)	N	S(3)	S(2)

Finally, the difference between column “Set of bindings size” and “Expanded templates size” in Table 3 confirms how the use of the PROV-Template approach for generating provenance reduces the storage requirements for the set of bindings compared to the expanded templates.

1.1.4 Aspect 5: Quality of provenance

In this section we will focus on the quality of the provenance generated from the University example. To analyse this aspect, we study if the collected provenance answers *completely* (C), *sufficiently* (S), *partially* (P) or it cannot answer (N) the questions in Table 2.

Completely When the user indicated that the answer was more detailed than what she/he expected.

Sufficiently When the user indicated that the level of detail was enough.

Partially When the answer did not satisfy the user.

No When it was not possible to answer the question.

Table 4 summarizes our conclusions, showing the number of elements (*prov:Entity*, *prov:Activity*, and *prov:Agent*) involved in such an answer, when it can be responded (i.e., when the response is not classified as N). Based on these results, we identified three kinds of implications the mode used to tailor the UML design may have on the answers.

No effect. The followed mode had *no effect* on the ability to answer to questions Q2 and Q5. More specifically, the answer to questions Q2 and Q5 relies upon the values of attributes belonging to the class Exam. Since the three modes take into account a CD with all the attributes of class Exam, the provenance obtained from can answer these questions.

More detailed information. The answer to Q1 relies upon the operations identified in classes Exam, Teacher, and Student. Mode 1, which only identifies a set of operations, answers Q1 with a sufficient number of elements (5). However, Modes 2 and 3, encompassing the whole operations, answers Q1 with more elements than necessary (12 both of them).

Crucial. The UML diagrams supported by UML2PROV model only certain aspects of an application’s behaviour. Consequently, the generated provenance will contain information about these aspects. The answer to question Q3 relies upon information provided by SMDs; thus, Mode 1, which is the only one considering SMDs, is the unique mode capable for answering Q3.

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INTEGRATING PROVENANCE CAPTURE AND UML WITH UML2PROV: PRINCIPLES AND EXPERIENCE

OCL CONSTRAINTS

Carlos Sáenz-Adán^{1*}, Beatriz Pérez¹, Francisco J. García-Izquierdo¹, Luc Moreau²

¹*Dept. of Mathematics and Computer Science, Univ. of La Rioja, La Rioja, Spain,
{carlos.saenz,beatriz.perez,francisco.garcia}@unirioja.es*

²*Dept. of Informatics, King's College London, London, UK,
luc.moreau@kcl.ac.uk*

These constraints (from OCL1 to OCL5) mainly impose interconnections among (OCL1 and OCL2) senders/receivers in SqD and objects modelled by SMD, (OCL3 and OCL4) incoming/outgoing messages in SqD with events/actions in SMD, and (OCL5) incoming messages in SqD with methods in objects modelled by SMD.

(OCL1-2) Each sender of a message in an interaction of a SqD must be an object modelled by a SMD. The same constraint is defined for a receiver, changing sender by receiver.

```
context: Interaction
inv: self.message.sender.base.behavior &#x27E; notEmpty ()
```

(OCL3) Incoming messages to an object within a SqD are events in a SMD.

```
context: Message
inv: self.receiver.base.behavior.region.transition.trigger->exists(e|e.name=self.name)
```

(OCL4) Outgoing messages of an object within a SqD are actions in a SMD.

```
context: Message
inv: self.sender.base.behavior.region.transition.effect->exists(e|e.name=self.name)
```

(OCL5) Incoming messages of an object (receiver) within SqD must be object's methods.

```
context: Message
inv: let rec:ClassifiedRole = self.receiver in
      let ops:Operation = rec.base.ownedOperation in
      ops -> exists(oper| oper.name = self.name)
```